

Supplementary Material for Renormalising Generative Models for Active Inference

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Scope of this supplement

This supplementary document collects the longer derivations, fixed-point accounts, reference-algorithm comparisons, and structure-learning details that support the main paper. It is intended to be read as a standalone technical companion rather than as an appendix embedded in the main manuscript.

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1 Variational Inference and Variational Message Passing

This section fixes the variational-inference background used throughout the RGM explanation. Variational message passing gives the canonical local-update account that later makes the roles of likelihood, transition, and hierarchical mapping factors transparent.

1.1 The ELBO From the Reverse KL

Assume we have an observed variable x and a latent variable θ . Our likelihood is $p(x | \theta)$ and our prior is $p(\theta)$. We want to approximate the posterior $p(\theta | x)$ with a variational distribution $q(\theta)$. Consider the reverse KL divergence:

$$D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta | x)) = \int q(\theta) \log \frac{q(\theta)}{p(\theta | x)} d\theta.$$

Using Bayes' rule,

$$p(\theta | x) = \frac{p(x | \theta)p(\theta)}{p(x)},$$

we get

$$\begin{aligned} D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta | x)) &= \int q(\theta) \log q(\theta) d\theta - \int q(\theta) \log p(x | \theta) d\theta \\ &\quad - \int q(\theta) \log p(\theta) d\theta + \int q(\theta) \log p(x) d\theta. \end{aligned}$$

Since $\log p(x)$ does not depend on θ ,

$$\int q(\theta) \log p(x) d\theta = \log p(x),$$

because $\int q(\theta) d\theta = 1$. Therefore,

$$D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta | x)) = -\mathbb{E}_{q(\theta)}[\log p(x | \theta)] + D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta)) + \log p(x).$$

Rearranging gives

$$\log p(x) - D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta | x)) = \mathbb{E}_{q(\theta)}[\log p(x | \theta)] - D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta)).$$

The right-hand side is the evidence lower bound (ELBO):

$$\text{ELBO}(q) = \mathbb{E}_{q(\theta)}[\log p(x | \theta)] - D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta)).$$

Equivalently, since $p(x, \theta) = p(x | \theta)p(\theta)$,

$$\text{ELBO}(q) = \mathbb{E}_q[\log p(x, \theta)] - \mathbb{E}_q[\log q(\theta)].$$

Because

$$\log p(x) = \text{ELBO}(q) + D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta | x)),$$

and $\log p(x)$ does not depend on q , maximizing the ELBO is equivalent to minimizing the KL divergence from $q(\theta)$ to the true posterior. If the KL divergence is zero, then $q(\theta) = p(\theta | x)$ almost everywhere, and the ELBO equals the true log evidence $\log p(x)$.

1.2 Mean-Field Factorization

Now assume a mean-field factorization

$$q(\theta) = \prod_i q_i(\theta_i),$$

where the latent variables have been partitioned into groups $\theta_1, \theta_2, \dots$, and the variational approximation factorizes across these groups. In the classical mean-field derivation, we usually assume only this factorization, not a specific parametric family for each factor q_i .

Recall that

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ELBO}(q) &= \mathbb{E}_q[\log p(x \mid \theta)] - D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \parallel p(\theta)) \\ &= \int q(\theta) \log p(x \mid \theta) d\theta - \int q(\theta) \log \frac{q(\theta)}{p(\theta)} d\theta \\ &= \int q(\theta) \log p(x, \theta) d\theta - \int q(\theta) \log q(\theta) d\theta. \end{aligned}$$

To derive the update for one factor q_i , write

$$q(\theta) = q_i(\theta_i) q_{-i}(\theta_{-i}), \quad q_{-i}(\theta_{-i}) = \prod_{j \neq i} q_j(\theta_j).$$

Substituting into the ELBO gives

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ELBO}(q) &= \int q_i(\theta_i) q_{-i}(\theta_{-i}) \log p(x, \theta) d\theta_i d\theta_{-i} \\ &\quad - \int q_i(\theta_i) q_{-i}(\theta_{-i}) \log(q_i(\theta_i) q_{-i}(\theta_{-i})) d\theta_i d\theta_{-i}. \end{aligned}$$

For brevity, write $q_i = q_i(\theta_i)$ and $q_{-i} = q_{-i}(\theta_{-i})$. Expanding the logarithm,

$$\log(q_i q_{-i}) = \log q_i + \log q_{-i},$$

so

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ELBO}(q) &= \int q_i q_{-i} \log p(x, \theta) d\theta_i d\theta_{-i} - \int q_i q_{-i} \log q_i d\theta_i d\theta_{-i} \\ &\quad - \int q_i q_{-i} \log q_{-i} d\theta_i d\theta_{-i}. \end{aligned}$$

Define

$$f(\theta_i) := \mathbb{E}_{q_{-i}}[\log p(x, \theta)].$$

Then the first term becomes

$$\int q_i(\theta_i) f(\theta_i) d\theta_i.$$

The second term simplifies to

$$\int q_i(\theta_i) \log q_i(\theta_i) d\theta_i,$$

because $\int q_{-i}(\theta_{-i}) d\theta_{-i} = 1$.

The third term is constant with respect to q_i when all other factors are held fixed, so it can be absorbed into an additive constant. Hence

$$\text{ELBO}(q) = \int q_i(\theta_i) f(\theta_i) d\theta_i - \int q_i(\theta_i) \log q_i(\theta_i) d\theta_i + \text{const.}$$

This expression is close to the negative of a KL divergence. The first term averages a function $f(\theta_i)$ under q_i , while the second term subtracts the entropy-like term $\int q_i(\theta_i) \log q_i(\theta_i) d\theta_i$. If $f(\theta_i)$ were the logarithm of a normalized distribution over θ_i , then maximizing the ELBO with respect to q_i would simply mean making q_i as close as possible to that distribution. The next step makes this intuition precise by turning $\exp(f(\theta_i))$ into a normalized density.

We now maximize this expression with respect to q_i . Define the unnormalized quantity

$$\rho_i(\theta_i) = \exp(f(\theta_i)).$$

Assuming this is normalizable, define

$$q_i^*(\theta_i) = \frac{1}{Z_i} \exp(f(\theta_i)), \quad Z_i = \int \exp(f(\theta_i)) d\theta_i.$$

Then

$$\log q_i^*(\theta_i) = f(\theta_i) - \log Z_i.$$

Substituting this into the ELBO gives

$$\begin{aligned} \text{ELBO}(q) &= \int q_i(\theta_i) \log q_i^*(\theta_i) d\theta_i - \int q_i(\theta_i) \log q_i(\theta_i) d\theta_i + \text{const} \\ &= -D_{\text{KL}}(q_i(\theta_i) \parallel q_i^*(\theta_i)) + \text{const.} \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, maximizing the ELBO with respect to q_i is equivalent to minimizing

$$D_{\text{KL}}(q_i(\theta_i) \parallel q_i^*(\theta_i)).$$

Since KL divergence is nonnegative, the maximum is attained exactly when

$$q_i(\theta_i) = q_i^*(\theta_i).$$

Thus the optimal mean-field update is

$$q_i^*(\theta_i) \propto \exp\left(\mathbb{E}_{q_{-i}}[\log p(x, \theta)]\right),$$

or equivalently,

$$\log q_i^*(\theta_i) = \mathbb{E}_{q_{-i}}[\log p(x, \theta)] + \text{const.}$$

So, under mean-field variational Bayes, each factor is updated by holding the other factors fixed and replacing q_i with the distribution that makes this KL divergence zero. Cycling through the factors in this way yields coordinate ascent on the ELBO.

1.3 Local VMP Updates From Graph Factorization

Variational message passing adds one more key observation. Suppose the full joint distribution factorizes according to a Bayesian network:

$$p(x, \theta) = \prod_j p(Z_j \mid \text{pa}_j),$$

where the Z_j denote all variables in the graph, both observed and latent, and pa_j denotes the parents of node Z_j . Then

$$\log p(x, \theta) = \sum_j \log p(Z_j \mid \text{pa}_j).$$

Substituting this into the mean-field update gives

$$\begin{aligned} \log q_i^*(\theta_i) &= \mathbb{E}_{q_{-i}}[\log p(x, \theta)] + \text{const} \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{q_{-i}} \left[\sum_j \log p(Z_j \mid \text{pa}_j) \right] + \text{const} \\ &= \sum_j \mathbb{E}_{q_{-i}}[\log p(Z_j \mid \text{pa}_j)] + \text{const}. \end{aligned}$$

Any term in this sum that does not involve θ_i is constant with respect to θ_i , so it can be absorbed into the additive constant. If q_i corresponds to a single node θ_i , then in a directed graphical model the only factors that involve θ_i are:

1. the factor for θ_i itself,

$$p(\theta_i \mid \text{pa}_i),$$

2. the factors for its children,

$$p(c \mid \text{pa}_c) \quad \text{for each child } c \in \text{ch}(\theta_i).$$

So the update for q_i depends only on the local neighborhood of θ_i in the graph. More precisely, it depends only on the Markov blanket of θ_i : its parents, its children, and the co-parents of its children.

The local mean-field update can therefore be written directly in terms of θ_i as

$$\log q_i^*(\theta_i) = \mathbb{E}_{q_{-i}}[\log p(\theta_i \mid \text{pa}_i)] + \sum_{j \in \text{ch}(\theta_i)} \mathbb{E}_{q_{-i}}[\log p(Z_j \mid \theta_i, \text{cp}_j)] + \text{const},$$

where q_{-i} denotes the variational distribution over all variables other than θ_i , and cp_j denotes the co-parents of θ_i for child Z_j .

This is the basis of variational message passing: under mean-field factorization, each variational factor can be updated using only the terms in the joint distribution that involve that variable. This leads to local, message-passing-style updates in the graph.

In the RGM sections below, the generic latent variable θ is specialized into hidden states s , paths u , and random parameters such as A , B , D , and E . The same mean-field rule still applies. The only change is notational: posterior categorical expectations will be written with hats, such as \hat{s}_τ and \hat{u}_τ , while posterior Dirichlet counts will be written with tildes, such as \tilde{a} and \tilde{b} .

1.4 Variational Free Energy

Variational free energy is just the negative ELBO:

$$F(q) = -\text{ELBO}(q).$$

Since

$$\text{ELBO}(q) = \mathbb{E}_q[\log p(x, \theta)] - \mathbb{E}_q[\log q(\theta)],$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} F(q) &= \mathbb{E}_q[\log q(\theta)] - \mathbb{E}_q[\log p(x, \theta)] \\ &= \mathbb{E}_q\left[\log \underbrace{q(\theta)}_{\text{posterior}} - \log \underbrace{p(x | \theta)}_{\text{likelihood}} - \log \underbrace{p(\theta)}_{\text{prior}}\right]. \end{aligned}$$

Using the usual ELBO decomposition,

$$\text{ELBO}(q) = \mathbb{E}_q[\log p(x | \theta)] - D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta)),$$

we can also write

$$F(q) = \underbrace{D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta))}_{\text{complexity}} - \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_q[\log p(x | \theta)]}_{\text{accuracy}}.$$

The complexity term measures how far the approximate posterior moves away from the prior. The accuracy term measures how well the latent causes favored by $q(\theta)$ explain the observed data x .

Finally, since

$$\text{ELBO}(q) = \log p(x) - D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta | x)),$$

we get

$$F(q) = \underbrace{D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta | x))}_{\text{divergence}} - \underbrace{\log p(x)}_{\text{evidence}}.$$

In the RGM case, θ may include hidden states, paths, and random parameters such as A , while x corresponds to observed outcomes.

2 Expected Free Energy and Planning

2.1 Expected Free Energy

2.1.1 Epistemic and Pragmatic Form Variational free energy is about inference after observing data. Expected free energy is about action selection before future data are observed.

For VFE, the observation x is already known. For EFE, the future observation is still unknown, so we evaluate a policy in terms of its predicted consequences. To see the basic idea, consider:

- a future hidden state s ,
- a future observation o ,
- a candidate policy u .

Under policy u , suppose we have the predictive distributions

$$q(s | u), \quad q(o | s), \quad q(o, s | u) = q(o | s) q(s | u).$$

We also introduce a preference distribution over outcomes,

$$p_{\text{pref}}(o),$$

which encodes which outcomes are preferred. When preferences are represented as a categorical parameter C , this means

$$p_{\text{pref}}(o = i) = C_i.$$

If that preference parameter is treated as uncertain, it can be assigned a Dirichlet prior,

$$C \sim \text{Dir}(c).$$

The resulting preferred-outcome distribution can be written compactly as $P(o | c)$. A minimal definition of expected free energy is

$$G(u) = \mathbb{E}_{q(o,s|u)} \left[\log q(s | u) - \log q(s | o, u) - \log p_{\text{pref}}(o) \right].$$

Now split this into two parts:

$$G(u) = - \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_{q(o,s|u)} \left[\log q(s | o, u) - \log q(s | u) \right]}_{\text{expected information gain}} - \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_{q(o,s|u)} [\log p_{\text{pref}}(o)]}_{\text{expected cost}}.$$

The first term is exactly the mutual information between s and o under policy u :

$$\mathbb{E}_{q(o,s|u)} \left[\log q(s | o, u) - \log q(s | u) \right] = I_q(s; o | u).$$

So

$$G(u) = -I_q(s; o | u) - \mathbb{E}_{q(o|u)} [\log p_{\text{pref}}(o)].$$

This makes the two roles of EFE clear:

- $-I_q(s; o | u)$ is the epistemic term. Minimizing G favors policies with larger expected information gain.
- $-\mathbb{E}_{q(o|u)}[\log p_{\text{pref}}(o)]$ is the pragmatic term. Minimizing G favors policies that lead to preferred outcomes.

So EFE combines exploration and goal-directed behavior in a single objective.

2.1.2 Risk and Ambiguity Form

$$G(u) = \mathbb{E}_{q(o,s|u)} \left[\log q(s | u) - \log q(s | o, u) - \log p_{\text{pref}}(o) \right].$$

Now use Bayes' rule inside the predictive model:

$$q(s | o, u) = \frac{q(o | s, u) q(s | u)}{q(o | u)}.$$

If the policy affects outcomes only through hidden states, then

$$q(o | s, u) = q(o | s),$$

so

$$q(s | o, u) = \frac{q(o | s) q(s | u)}{q(o | u)}.$$

Taking logs gives

$$\log q(s | o, u) = \log q(o | s) + \log q(s | u) - \log q(o | u).$$

Rearranging,

$$\log q(s | u) - \log q(s | o, u) = -\log q(o | s) + \log q(o | u).$$

Substituting into $G(u)$ gives

$$G(u) = \mathbb{E}_{q(o,s|u)} \left[\log q(o | u) - \log p_{\text{pref}}(o) - \log q(o | s) \right].$$

Now separate the terms:

$$G(u) = D_{\text{KL}}(q(o | u) \| p_{\text{pref}}(o)) - \mathbb{E}_{q(o,s|u)}[\log q(o | s)].$$

The second term can be rewritten as

$$-\mathbb{E}_{q(o,s|u)}[\log q(o | s)] = \mathbb{E}_{q(s|u)}[H(q(o | s))].$$

So we obtain

$$G(u) = \underbrace{D_{\text{KL}}(q(o | u) \| p_{\text{pref}}(o))}_{\text{risk}} + \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_{q(s|u)}[H(q(o | s))]}_{\text{ambiguity}}.$$

This is the other standard form of EFE:

- Risk measures how far predicted outcomes are from preferred outcomes.
- Ambiguity measures how noisy observations are, even if the hidden state were known.

2.2 Expected Free Energy in RGMs

In RGMs, the latent variables are richer. We have hidden states s , random parameters such as A , outcomes o , and policies or paths u . The corresponding Dirichlet counts are written with lowercase symbols such as a , but the random parameter itself is A .

Friston et al. [1] write

$$G(u) = \mathbb{E}_{Q_u} \left[\log Q(s, A | u) - \log Q(s, A | o, u) - \log P(o | c) \right].$$

This is the same basic construction as above, except that the latent variable is now (s, A) instead of just s , and preferences are written as $P(o | c)$ instead of the generic $p_{\text{pref}}(o)$. To match Equation 2 of Friston et al. [1], this derivation uses uppercase Q for posterior and posterior predictive distributions.

Start from

$$G(u) = \mathbb{E}_{Q_u} \left[\log Q(s, A | u) - \log Q(s, A | o, u) - \log P(o | c) \right].$$

Apply the chain rule:

$$\log Q(s, A | u) = \log Q(A | s, u) + \log Q(s | u),$$

and

$$\log Q(s, A | o, u) = \log Q(A | s, o, u) + \log Q(s | o, u).$$

Subtracting gives

$$\log Q(s, A | u) - \log Q(s, A | o, u) = \left[\log Q(A | s, u) - \log Q(A | s, o, u) \right] + \left[\log Q(s | u) - \log Q(s | o, u) \right].$$

So

$$\begin{aligned} G(u) = & - \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_{Q_u} \left[\log Q(A | s, o, u) - \log Q(A | s, u) \right]}_{\text{expected information gain (learning)}} \\ & - \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_{Q_u} \left[\log Q(s | o, u) - \log Q(s | u) \right]}_{\text{expected information gain (inference)}} \\ & - \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_{Q_u} [\log P(o | c)]}_{\text{expected cost}}. \end{aligned}$$

This is the decomposition shown in Equation 2 of Friston et al. [1]. The first information-gain term can be rewritten as

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}_{Q_u} \left[\log Q(A | s, o, u) - \log Q(A | s, u) \right] \\ &= \sum_{s, o} Q(s, o | u) \int Q(A | s, o, u) \left[\log Q(A | s, o, u) - \log Q(A | s, u) \right] dA \\ &= \sum_{s, o} Q(s, o | u) D_{\text{KL}}(Q(A | s, o, u) \| Q(A | s, u)) \\ &= \mathbb{E}_{Q(s, o | u)} \left[D_{\text{KL}}(Q(A | s, o, u) \| Q(A | s, u)) \right]. \end{aligned}$$

This corresponds to the novelty term in the final line of Equation 2 of Friston et al. [1]. Likewise, the second information-gain term becomes an expected KL divergence over hidden states, and the final expression can be rewritten in terms of novelty, risk, and ambiguity.

2.3 Planning as Inference

Expected free energy defines a prior over policies:

$$P(u) \propto \exp(-G(u)).$$

So policies with lower expected free energy become more probable. This is the sense in which planning is cast as inference. In practice, this prior is usually written with a baseline path prior π^u and a precision parameter α :

$$q(u = h) = \pi_G(h) := \text{norm}_h(\pi_h^u e^{-\alpha G_h}).$$

The parameter α controls how decisively differences in expected free energy shape posterior policy beliefs. When α is small, several policies can retain appreciable posterior probability even if their expected free energies differ. When α is large, the posterior concentrates on the policies with the lowest expected free energy.

For temporal models, expected free energy can be evaluated over a finite planning horizon. Let T be the final time point of the current epoch, and let N be the maximum depth of recursive policy search. At time τ , the terminal search time is

$$n = \min(T, \tau + N).$$

The immediate consequences of each candidate path or policy are always scored first: predict the next hidden state, predict the next outcome, and evaluate the expected free energy of that prediction. If $\tau < n$, the search then continues recursively. The model predicts likely future states and outcomes, updates beliefs under those possible futures, evaluates later policies, and adds their expected scores to the current policy score.

Thus $N = 0$ gives one-step policy scoring only. Larger N adds recursive lookahead, but not an exhaustive enumeration of every possible future. The search is selective: it follows likely policies under likely hidden states and accumulates the expected future score back into the value of the next policy.

3 Static RGMs

Before starting the worked examples, one notation convention is worth fixing. Bare symbols such as s , o , A , and D denote random variables or parameters. Posterior categorical expectations are written with hats, for example $\hat{s}_j := q(s = j)$. Posterior Dirichlet counts are written with tildes, for example \tilde{a} and \tilde{d} .

A hidden-state factor is one categorical latent variable. A state is one possible value of that factor. In the simplest example below there is only one hidden-state

factor, so writing $s = j$ is unambiguous. Later, when several factors are present, $s^f = j$ will mean that factor f is in its j -th state.

The minimal examples below derive canonical VMP updates for static RGMs before the temporal and algorithmic complications are introduced.

3.1 A Minimal Likelihood Model

Assume one hidden state $s \in \{1, \dots, K_s\}$, one observation $o \in \{1, \dots, K_o\}$, and one random likelihood matrix $A \in [0, 1]^{K_o \times K_s}$. Each column of A is a categorical distribution, so

$$\sum_{i=1}^{K_o} A_{ij} = 1 \quad \text{for each } j.$$

Thus column j defines the distribution of o conditional on $s = j$:

$$p(o = i \mid s = j, A) = A_{ij}.$$

The prior over hidden states is

$$p(s = j) = \pi_j, \quad \pi_j \geq 0, \quad \sum_{j=1}^{K_s} \pi_j = 1.$$

The prior over A factorizes by columns:

$$p(A) = \prod_{j=1}^{K_s} p(A_{\cdot j}), \quad A_{\cdot j} \sim \text{Dir}(a_{\cdot j}).$$

Write

$$a_{0j} := \sum_{i=1}^{K_o} a_{ij}.$$

Then the prior mean of A_{ij} is

$$\mathbb{E}[A_{ij}] = \frac{a_{ij}}{a_{0j}},$$

and

$$\mathbb{E}[\log A_{ij}] = \psi(a_{ij}) - \psi(a_{0j}).$$

Our goal is to approximate the posterior

$$q(s, A) \approx p(s, A \mid o).$$

Under a mean-field variational approximation, we write

$$q(s, A) = q(s) q(A).$$

To avoid overloading notation, it is useful to distinguish:

- the realised observation $o = i^*$, where $i^* \in \{1, \dots, K_o\}$;
- the one-hot encoding $o \in \{0, 1\}^{K_o}$, with $o_{i^*} = 1$.

These are two equivalent ways of representing the same observation.

3.1.1 Updating s To update the hidden-state factor, we use the mean-field VMP update

$$\log q^*(s = j) = \log p(s = j) + \mathbb{E}_{q(A)}[\log p(o = i^* \mid s = j, A)] + \text{const.}$$

Since

$$p(s = j) = \pi_j$$

and

$$p(o = i^* \mid s = j, A) = A_{i^*j},$$

this becomes

$$\log q^*(s = j) = \log \pi_j + \mathbb{E}_{q(A)}[\log A_{i^*j}] + \text{const.}$$

Now suppose the current variational posterior over each column of A is also Dirichlet:

$$q(A) = \prod_j \text{Dir}(A_{.j} \mid \tilde{a}_{.j}), \quad \tilde{a}_{0j} := \sum_i \tilde{a}_{ij}.$$

Then

$$\mathbb{E}_{q(A)}[\log A_{i^*j}] = \psi(\tilde{a}_{i^*j}) - \psi(\tilde{a}_{0j}).$$

Therefore

$$\log q^*(s = j) = \log \pi_j + \psi(\tilde{a}_{i^*j}) - \psi(\tilde{a}_{0j}) + \text{const.}$$

Exponentiating gives

$$q^*(s = j) \propto \exp(\log \pi_j + \psi(\tilde{a}_{i^*j}) - \psi(\tilde{a}_{0j})).$$

Normalizing over j gives a categorical distribution, i.e. a softmax update:

$$q^*(s = j) = \frac{\exp(\log \pi_j + \psi(\tilde{a}_{i^*j}) - \psi(\tilde{a}_{0j}))}{\sum_k \exp(\log \pi_k + \psi(\tilde{a}_{i^*k}) - \psi(\tilde{a}_{0k}))}.$$

Equivalently, in vector form,

$$q^*(s) = \sigma(\log \pi + m_{\uparrow A}),$$

where the likelihood message is

$$m_{\uparrow A} = o \odot \varphi(\tilde{a}).$$

Here

$$\varphi(\tilde{a})_{ij} = \psi(\tilde{a}_{ij}) - \psi(\tilde{a}_{0j}),$$

and $o \odot \varphi(\tilde{a})$ denotes contraction over the observation index i . Componentwise,

$$(m_{\uparrow A})_j = \sum_{i=1}^{K_o} o_i \varphi(\tilde{a})_{ij} = \sum_{i=1}^{K_o} o_i (\psi(\tilde{a}_{ij}) - \psi(\tilde{a}_{0j})).$$

If o is one-hot at $i = i^*$, this reduces to

$$(m_{\uparrow A})_j = \psi(\tilde{a}_{i^*j}) - \psi(\tilde{a}_{0j}).$$

In the notation of Friston et al. [1],

$$q(s) = \sigma(\log \pi + m_{\uparrow A}), \quad m_{\uparrow A} = o \odot \varphi(\tilde{a}).$$

A small notation point is worth flagging before moving on. It is useful to distinguish:

- the evidence-conditioned outcome O supplied to inference as data, either as a one-hot vector with $o_{i^*} = 1$ or, more generally, as a distribution over $\{1, \dots, K_o\}$ representing uncertainty about which one-hot outcome was observed;
- the posterior predictive outcome $\hat{o} := Q(o)$ produced after inference by pushing the inferred state belief back through the likelihood:

$$\hat{o}_i := Q(o = i) = \sum_j P(o = i \mid s = j) Q(s = j), \quad \hat{o} = \mu(\tilde{a}) \odot Q(s).$$

For temporal and multimodal models we will write these as $O_{g,t}$ and $\hat{o}_{g,t} := Q(o_t^g)$, with g indexing the observation modality and t the time step. The two objects look similar, because both live on the outcome simplex, but they play different roles: O is evidence going into inference, while \hat{o} is a prediction coming out of it. In particular, a soft O does not mean the world emitted a probability vector; it encodes the agent’s uncertainty about an underlying one-hot observation.

3.1.2 Updating A

For the likelihood matrix, the mean-field update is

$$\log q^*(A) = \log p(A) + \mathbb{E}_{q(s)}[\log p(o \mid s, A)] + \text{const.}$$

Since the prior factorizes by columns,

$$p(A) = \prod_j \text{Dir}(A_{\cdot j} \mid a_{\cdot j}),$$

we get

$$\log q^*(A) = \sum_j \log \text{Dir}(A_{\cdot j} \mid a_{\cdot j}) + \mathbb{E}_{q(s)}[\log p(o \mid s, A)] + \text{const.}$$

Now write both s and o as one-hot vectors. Then

$$\log p(o \mid s, A) = \sum_j s_j \sum_i o_i \log A_{ij}.$$

Taking expectation with respect to $q(s)$ gives

$$\mathbb{E}_{q(s)}[\log p(o | s, A)] = \sum_j \hat{s}_j \sum_i o_i \log A_{ij},$$

where

$$\hat{s}_j := q(s = j).$$

Therefore

$$\log q^*(A) = \sum_j \log \text{Dir}(A_{.j} | a_{.j}) + \sum_j \hat{s}_j \sum_i o_i \log A_{ij} + \text{const.}$$

Expanding the Dirichlet term,

$$\log \text{Dir}(A_{.j} | a_{.j}) = \sum_i (a_{ij} - 1) \log A_{ij} + \text{const.},$$

so

$$\log q^*(A) = \sum_j \sum_i (a_{ij} - 1 + \hat{s}_j o_i) \log A_{ij} + \text{const.}$$

For a fixed column j , this is

$$\log q^*(A_{.j}) = \sum_i (a_{ij} - 1 + \hat{s}_j o_i) \log A_{ij} + \text{const.}$$

This is exactly the log-density of a Dirichlet distribution. Therefore

$$q^*(A_{.j}) = \text{Dir}(A_{.j} | a_{.j} + \hat{s}_j o).$$

So each column of A is updated by adding a fractional count \hat{s}_j times the observed one-hot vector o . Collecting all columns together, the full update can be written as

$$q^*(A) = \prod_j \text{Dir}(A_{.j} | a_{.j} + \hat{s}_j o),$$

or equivalently, at the level of concentration parameters,

$$\tilde{a} = a + o \otimes \hat{s},$$

with componentwise form

$$\tilde{a}_{ij} = a_{ij} + o_i \hat{s}_j.$$

3.2 A Two-Level Static Hierarchy

We now introduce a simple static hierarchy with

- higher-level state $s^{(2)} \in \{1, \dots, K_2\}$;
- lower-level state $s^{(1)} \in \{1, \dots, K_1\}$;
- observation $o \in \{1, \dots, K_o\}$.

The key structural distinction is:

- A maps lower states to observations;
- D maps higher states to lower states.

So the generative model is

$$p(o, s^{(1)}, s^{(2)}, A, D) = p(s^{(2)}) p(D) p(s^{(1)} | s^{(2)}, D) p(A) p(o | s^{(1)}, A).$$

More explicitly,

$$\begin{aligned} p(s^{(2)} = j) &= \pi_j, \\ p(s^{(1)} = k | s^{(2)} = j, D) &= D_{kj}, \\ p(o = i | s^{(1)} = k, A) &= A_{ik}. \end{aligned}$$

Each column of A has a Dirichlet prior:

$$A_{.k} \sim \text{Dir}(a_{.k}),$$

and each column of D has a Dirichlet prior:

$$D_{.j} \sim \text{Dir}(d_{.j}).$$

Again, we approximate the posterior as

$$q(s^{(2)}, s^{(1)}, A, D) = q(s^{(2)}) q(s^{(1)}) q(A) q(D).$$

Let

$$\hat{s}_j^{(2)} := q(s^{(2)} = j), \quad \hat{s}_k^{(1)} := q(s^{(1)} = k).$$

Also write

$$q(A) = \prod_k \text{Dir}(A_{.k} | \tilde{a}_{.k}), \quad q(D) = \prod_j \text{Dir}(D_{.j} | \tilde{d}_{.j}).$$

As before, it is useful to let o also denote the one-hot encoding of the realised observation, so that

$$o_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if the observed outcome is } i, \\ 0 & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Define

$$\varphi(\tilde{a})_{ik} := \psi(\tilde{a}_{ik}) - \psi(\tilde{a}_{0k}), \quad \tilde{a}_{0k} := \sum_i \tilde{a}_{ik},$$

and similarly

$$\varphi(\tilde{d})_{kj} := \psi(\tilde{d}_{kj}) - \psi(\tilde{d}_{0j}), \quad \tilde{d}_{0j} := \sum_k \tilde{d}_{kj}.$$

3.2.1 Updating $s^{(1)}$ The mean-field update is

$$\log q^*(s^{(1)} = k) = \mathbb{E}_{q(s^{(2)})q(D)}[\log p(s^{(1)} = k | s^{(2)}, D)] + \mathbb{E}_{q(A)}[\log p(o | s^{(1)} = k, A)] + \text{const.}$$

Expanding,

$$\log q^*(s^{(1)} = k) = \sum_j \hat{s}_j^{(2)} \mathbb{E}[\log D_{kj}] + \sum_i o_i \mathbb{E}[\log A_{ik}] + \text{const.}$$

The likelihood term is exactly the same as in the one-level case, so define

$$m_{\uparrow A} = o \odot \varphi(\tilde{a}),$$

with components

$$(m_{\uparrow A})_k = \sum_i o_i \varphi(\tilde{a})_{ik}.$$

Likewise, the descending hierarchical message from D is

$$m_{\downarrow D} = \varphi(\tilde{d}) \odot \hat{s}^{(2)},$$

with components

$$(m_{\downarrow D})_k = \sum_j \hat{s}_j^{(2)} \varphi(\tilde{d})_{kj} = \sum_j \hat{s}_j^{(2)} \mathbb{E}[\log D_{kj}].$$

Therefore

$$q^*(s^{(1)}) = \sigma(m_{\downarrow D} + m_{\uparrow A}).$$

So the lower-level state is updated by combining a descending prior message from the higher level with an ascending likelihood message from the observation model.

3.2.2 Updating $s^{(2)}$ The update is

$$\log q^*(s^{(2)} = j) = \log \pi_j + \sum_k \hat{s}_k^{(1)} \mathbb{E}[\log D_{kj}] + \text{const.}$$

Define the ascending hierarchical message

$$m_{\uparrow D} = \hat{s}^{(1)} \odot \varphi(\tilde{d}),$$

with components

$$(m_{\uparrow D})_j = \sum_k \hat{s}_k^{(1)} \varphi(\tilde{d})_{kj} = \sum_k \hat{s}_k^{(1)} \mathbb{E}[\log D_{kj}].$$

Then

$$q^*(s^{(2)}) = \sigma(\log \pi + m_{\uparrow D}).$$

This is the static hierarchical analogue of the ascending D -message in Figure 2 of Friston et al. [1].

3.2.3 Updating A Exactly as in the one-level case,

$$q^*(A_{.k}) = \text{Dir}(A_{.k} \mid a_{.k} + \hat{s}_k^{(1)} o).$$

Equivalently,

$$\tilde{a} = a + o \otimes \hat{s}^{(1)},$$

with componentwise form

$$\tilde{a}_{ik} = a_{ik} + o_i \hat{s}_k^{(1)}.$$

3.2.4 Updating D We compute

$$\log q^*(D) = \log p(D) + \mathbb{E}_{q(s^{(1)})q(s^{(2)})}[\log p(s^{(1)} \mid s^{(2)}, D)] + \text{const.}$$

Using

$$\log p(s^{(1)} \mid s^{(2)}, D) = \sum_j s_j^{(2)} \sum_k s_k^{(1)} \log D_{kj},$$

and taking expectations under $q(s^{(1)})q(s^{(2)})$, we get

$$\mathbb{E}[\log p(s^{(1)} \mid s^{(2)}, D)] = \sum_j \hat{s}_j^{(2)} \sum_k \hat{s}_k^{(1)} \log D_{kj}.$$

So for each column j ,

$$q^*(D_{.j}) = \text{Dir}(D_{.j} \mid d_{.j} + \hat{s}_j^{(2)} \hat{s}^{(1)}).$$

Equivalently,

$$\tilde{d} = d + \hat{s}^{(1)} \otimes \hat{s}^{(2)}.$$

Componentwise,

$$\tilde{d}_{kj} = d_{kj} + \hat{s}_k^{(1)} \hat{s}_j^{(2)}.$$

So the D -matrix is updated by adding the outer product of posterior expectations over lower and higher states.

3.3 Multiple Children and Co-Parents

So far we derived updates in the simplest case: one hidden factor, one child, and one likelihood matrix. Now we extend the derivation in the two directions that matter:

1. one latent factor can have multiple children, so its total message is a sum of child messages;
2. one child can have multiple parents, so the message to any one parent is the expected log-likelihood averaged over the other parents.

This is exactly the pattern shown in Figure 2 of Friston et al. [1] for the A -messages, and the same logic later reappears for D and E .

3.3.1 One state with multiple outputs Suppose a hidden factor f generates several observation modalities $g \in \text{ch}(f)$. From the general VMP update,

$$\log q_i^*(\theta_i) = \mathbb{E}_{q_{-i}}[\log p(\theta_i \mid \text{pa}_i)] + \sum_{j \in \text{ch}(\theta_i)} \mathbb{E}_{q_{-i}}[\log p(Z_j \mid \theta_i, \text{cp}_j)] + \text{const},$$

each child contributes its own term to the update of the parent. So if a state factor has several observational children, their contributions simply add. Therefore the total likelihood message to factor f is

$$m_{\uparrow A}^f = \sum_{g \in \text{ch}(f)} m_{\uparrow A}^{g,f}.$$

So the total ascending A -message is just the sum of the messages from each child modality.

3.3.2 One output with multiple parents Now consider the other extension: one observation modality depends on several hidden factors at the same level. Then the likelihood is a tensor rather than a matrix. To keep the notation simple, suppose one modality o^g depends on two hidden factors,

$$s^1 \in \{1, \dots, K_1\}, \quad s^2 \in \{1, \dots, K_2\}.$$

Then

$$p(o^g = i \mid s^1 = j, s^2 = k, A^g) = A_{ijk}^g,$$

so each slice A_{ijk}^g is a categorical distribution over outcomes and carries a Dirichlet prior.

When updating $q(s^1)$, we keep only the terms that involve s^1 . For an observed outcome encoded as a one-hot vector o^g , that gives

$$\log q^*(s^1 = j) = \log \pi_j^1 + \sum_i o_i^g \sum_k \hat{s}_k^2 \mathbb{E}[\log A_{ijk}^g] + \text{const}.$$

Equivalently, we can write this as

$$m_{\uparrow A}^{g,1} = o^g \odot \varphi(\tilde{a}^g) \odot \hat{s}^2.$$

By symmetry,

$$m_{\uparrow A}^{g,2} = o^g \odot \varphi(\tilde{a}^g) \odot \hat{s}^1.$$

When updating one parent, we contract the expected-log-likelihood tensor with the observation and with the posterior expectations over all the other parents. Therefore, in the general case,

$$m_{\uparrow A}^{g,f} = o^g \odot \varphi(\tilde{a}^g) \odot_{i \in \text{pa}(g) \setminus f} \hat{s}^i.$$

For the likelihood tensor A , the learning rule is the same idea in count form. For the two-parent example,

$$\tilde{a}^g = a^g + o^g \otimes \hat{s}^1 \otimes \hat{s}^2.$$

Nothing conceptually new happens in the general case: we simply take the outer product over all parents,

$$\tilde{a}^g = a^g + o^g \otimes_{i \in pa(g)} \hat{s}^i.$$

3.3.3 Multiple child states and multiple parent states The same pattern reappears for hierarchical mappings.

If one parent state generates several child states, the total upward message is again a sum over children, just as with multiple observation modalities:

$$m_{\uparrow D}^f = \sum_{d \in ch(f)} m_{\uparrow D}^{d,f}.$$

If one child state has several parents, then the message to one parent is again obtained by averaging the expected log-factor over the other parents. So the D -message is the direct hierarchical analogue of the A -message:

$$m_{\uparrow D}^{d,f} = \hat{s}_0^d \odot \varphi(\tilde{d}^d) \odot_{i \in pa(d) \setminus f} \hat{s}^i.$$

Likewise, the learning rule has the same outer-product form:

$$\tilde{d}^f = d^f + \hat{s}_0^f \otimes_{i \in pa(f)} \hat{s}^i.$$

So once the A -case is clear, the D -case is really the same algebra with different variables.

The one new update is the message passed to the child state when it has multiple parents. In that case, the descending message is

$$m_{\downarrow D}^f = \varphi(\tilde{d}^f) \odot_{i \in pa(f)} \hat{s}^i.$$

3.3.4 The Static RGM Partition Figure 2 of Friston et al. [1] gives message-passing expressions for a fairly general factor graph. In that general account, an observed modality or a lower-level latent variable can have several parent factors. The tensor contractions above are needed precisely because the message to one parent must average over the posterior beliefs of its co-parents.

The RGM hierarchy restricts that general case. In the static picture, a higher state may generate a group of lower-level states through several D links, but each lower-level state belongs to one such vertical group: it is not shared by several higher-level parents. Thus the restriction is that each child has one parent at the level above.

For the algebra in this section, that restriction removes the co-parent contractions from the vertical D links. The general multi-parent D tensor collapses to a matrix for each parent-child link, and the descending message to a lower state becomes an ordinary contraction with its single parent belief. Different groups can still become statistically related through higher levels of the hierarchy, but the lower-level children do not couple their parent factors by being shared between them.

The full RGM statement is temporal as well as hierarchical: the same partition applies to lower-level paths, and a higher state generates finite lower-level trajectories by supplying initial states and paths. Those ingredients are introduced in the next section before the full structural summary is given.

4 Temporal RGMs

This section extends the canonical RGM model and VMP update derivations from static hierarchies to temporal states, paths, and higher-level initial-state and initial-path priors.

4.1 The Fixed-Path Temporal Model

We now move from the static case to the simplest temporal case. We still keep the model as simple as possible:

- one hidden-state factor;
- one observation modality;
- one likelihood matrix A ;
- one transition matrix B .

So the hidden state becomes a sequence

$$s_0, s_1, \dots, s_T,$$

with corresponding observations

$$o_0, o_1, \dots, o_T.$$

The generative model is

$$p(s_{0:T}, o_{0:T}, A, B) = p(A) p(B) p(s_0) \prod_{\tau=0}^T p(o_\tau | s_\tau, A) \prod_{\tau=1}^T p(s_\tau | s_{\tau-1}, B).$$

The new parameter is the transition matrix B . Its column indexed by the previous state defines a categorical distribution over the next state:

$$p(s_\tau = i | s_{\tau-1} = j, B) = B_{ij}.$$

As with the likelihood, the transition probabilities can be given Dirichlet priors column by column:

$$B_{\cdot j} \sim \text{Dir}(b_{\cdot j}).$$

This is the temporal analogue of the one-level static model, with one extra ingredient: transitions between successive hidden states.

4.1.1 Updating s_τ For an interior time point $1 \leq \tau \leq T - 1$, the relevant log-joint terms involving s_τ are:

1. the likelihood term, $\log p(o_\tau | s_\tau, A)$,
2. the transition into s_τ , $\log p(s_\tau | s_{\tau-1}, B)$,
3. the transition out of s_τ , $\log p(s_{\tau+1} | s_\tau, B)$.

So the mean-field update is

$$\log q^*(s_\tau) = \mathbb{E}[\log p(o_\tau | s_\tau, A)] + \mathbb{E}[\log p(s_\tau | s_{\tau-1}, B)] + \mathbb{E}[\log p(s_{\tau+1} | s_\tau, B)] + \text{const.}$$

Compared with the static case, there are now two new messages: one from the previous state and one from the next state. So the temporal hidden-state update has the form

$$q(s_\tau) = \sigma(m_{\uparrow A, \tau} + m_{\rightarrow B, \tau} + m_{\leftarrow B, \tau}).$$

The likelihood message is the same as before:

$$m_{\uparrow A, \tau} = o_\tau \odot \varphi(\tilde{a}),$$

with components

$$(m_{\uparrow A, \tau})_i = \sum_m o_{\tau, m} \varphi(\tilde{a})_{mi}.$$

The forward transition message comes from the factor

$$p(s_\tau = i | s_{\tau-1} = j, B) = B_{ij},$$

so

$$(m_{\rightarrow B, \tau})_i = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau-1, j} \mathbb{E}[\log B_{ij}] = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau-1, j} \varphi(\tilde{b})_{ij}.$$

Equivalently,

$$m_{\rightarrow B, \tau} = \varphi(\tilde{b}) \odot \hat{s}_{\tau-1}.$$

The backward transition message comes from the factor

$$p(s_{\tau+1} = k | s_\tau = i, B) = B_{ki},$$

so

$$(m_{\leftarrow B, \tau})_i = \sum_k \hat{s}_{\tau+1, k} \mathbb{E}[\log B_{ki}] = \sum_k \hat{s}_{\tau+1, k} \varphi(\tilde{b})_{ki}.$$

Equivalently,

$$m_{\leftarrow B, \tau} = \varphi(\tilde{b}^\top) \odot \hat{s}_{\tau+1}.$$

This is why Friston et al. [1] write the backward message using b^T : the same transition tensor is read in the reverse direction when updating the current state from the next state.

Putting the pieces together, for an interior time point we get

$$q^*(s_\tau) = \sigma(m_{\uparrow A, \tau} + m_{\rightarrow B, \tau} + m_{\leftarrow B, \tau}).$$

So the hidden-state posterior is still a softmax over incoming expected-log messages. The only new ingredient is that there are now transition messages from both neighboring timepoints.

At the initial timepoint, there is no previous state. So in the non-hierarchical temporal model,

$$q^*(s_0) = \sigma(\log p(s_0) + m_{\uparrow A, 0} + m_{\leftarrow B, 0}).$$

If the initial state is instead generated from a higher level, then $\log p(s_0)$ is replaced by the descending D -message, $m_{\downarrow D}$.

4.1.2 Updating B Now update B . This is exactly the same Dirichlet-count pattern as for A , except that the sufficient statistic now counts transitions between successive hidden states rather than co-occurrences of hidden states and observations.

For a single transition from $s_{\tau-1}$ to s_τ , the expected count is

$$\hat{s}_\tau \otimes \hat{s}_{\tau-1}.$$

So the local increment is

$$\tilde{b} = b + \hat{s}_\tau \otimes \hat{s}_{\tau-1}.$$

Over a full sequence, we sum over all transitions:

$$\tilde{b} = b + \sum_{\tau=1}^T \hat{s}_\tau \otimes \hat{s}_{\tau-1}.$$

So this is the temporal analogue of the static learning update:

– static likelihood learning:

$$\tilde{a} = a + o \otimes \hat{s},$$

– temporal transition learning:

$$\tilde{b} = b + \hat{s}_\tau \otimes \hat{s}_{\tau-1}.$$

In both cases, we are just adding expected counts to Dirichlet concentration parameters.

4.2 Paths and Higher-Level Priors

We now extend the temporal model by introducing a path variable u_τ , and by allowing a higher level to initialize the lower-level initial state s_0 through D and the initial path u_0 through E .

The basic idea is:

- the hidden state s_τ says which state is active at time τ ;
- the path u_τ says which transition regime is active.

So instead of

$$p(s_{\tau+1} | s_\tau, B),$$

we now have

$$p(s_{\tau+1} | s_\tau, u_\tau, B).$$

In Friston et al. [1], different values of u_τ select different transition slices of the transition tensor B . For one hidden-state factor, the transition tensor has entries

$$p(s_{\tau+1} = i | s_\tau = j, u_\tau = h, B) = B_{ijh}.$$

Each path value h therefore indexes one transition matrix. The corresponding Dirichlet prior is also slice-specific:

$$B_{\cdot,jh} \sim \text{Dir}(b_{\cdot,jh}).$$

A path factor is the categorical variable whose values select these transition regimes. Some path factors are controllable, meaning that planning can choose their values. Others are not controllable: their paths may still affect state transitions, but they are inferred as hidden causes of dynamics rather than selected as actions.

The mapping E plays the same hierarchical role for paths that D plays for states. If a higher-level state initializes a lower-level path factor, then

$$p(u_0^f = h | s^{\text{parent}} = j, E^f) = E_{hj}^f,$$

with Dirichlet prior

$$E_{\cdot,j}^f \sim \text{Dir}(e_{\cdot,j}^f).$$

4.2.1 Updating states s_τ For an interior timepoint, the state update still has the form

$$q(s_\tau) = \sigma(m_{\uparrow A, \tau} + m_{\rightarrow B, \tau} + m_{\leftarrow B, \tau}),$$

but the transition messages now depend on the path posteriors. The likelihood message is unchanged:

$$m_{\uparrow A, \tau} = o_\tau \odot \varphi(\tilde{a}).$$

The forward transition message becomes

$$(m_{\rightarrow B, \tau})_i = \sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j} \hat{u}_{\tau-1,h} \varphi(\tilde{b})_{ijh},$$

or equivalently

$$m_{\rightarrow B, \tau} = \varphi(\tilde{b}) \odot \hat{s}_{\tau-1} \odot \hat{u}_{\tau-1}.$$

Likewise, the backward transition message becomes

$$(m_{\leftarrow B, \tau})_i = \sum_{k,h} \hat{s}_{\tau+1,k} \hat{u}_{\tau,h} \varphi(\tilde{b})_{kih},$$

or equivalently

$$m_{\leftarrow B, \tau} = \varphi(\tilde{b}^\top) \odot \hat{s}_{\tau+1} \odot \hat{u}_\tau.$$

For s_0 , there is no previous transition, so the update uses the descending D -message instead:

$$q(s_0) = \sigma(m_{\uparrow A, 0} + m_{\leftarrow B, 0} + m_{\downarrow D}),$$

where

$$m_{\downarrow D} = \varphi(\tilde{d}) \odot_{i \in \text{pa}(f)} \hat{s}^i.$$

So introducing paths does not change the basic form of the state update. It only changes the transition messages by conditioning them on the currently inferred path.

4.2.2 Updating B With paths present, the sufficient statistic for one transition is now

$$\hat{s}_\tau \otimes \hat{s}_{\tau-1} \otimes \hat{u}_{\tau-1},$$

because the transition from $s_{\tau-1}$ to s_τ is selected by $u_{\tau-1}$. So the local increment is

$$\tilde{b} = b + \hat{s}_\tau \otimes \hat{s}_{\tau-1} \otimes \hat{u}_{\tau-1}.$$

Over a full sequence, we sum over time:

$$\tilde{b} = b + \sum_{\tau=1}^T \hat{s}_\tau \otimes \hat{s}_{\tau-1} \otimes \hat{u}_{\tau-1}.$$

This is exactly the transition analogue of the multi-parent A -update: we add expected counts over the child state, the parent state, and the path that selects the transition slice.

4.2.3 Updating u_τ For the initial path, Friston et al. [1] write

$$\hat{u}_0^f = \sigma\left(m_{\downarrow E}^f + m_{\text{prior}}^f\right),$$

where E is the hierarchical analogue of D , so

$$m_{\downarrow E}^f = \varphi(\tilde{e}^f) \odot_{i \in \text{pa}(f)} \hat{s}^i.$$

For later paths, Friston et al. [1] write

$$\hat{u}_{\tau-1}^f = \sigma\left(m_{\uparrow B}^f + m_{\text{prior}}^f\right),$$

where the upward message from the transition factor is

$$m_{\uparrow B}^f = \hat{s}_\tau^f \odot \varphi(\tilde{b}^f) \odot \hat{s}_{\tau-1}^f.$$

So the path posterior is updated using:

- evidence from the state transition through B ;
- a prior term m_{prior} .

This is the update used in Figure 2 of Friston et al. [1].

Section 5 separates these issues: the reference parent-child algorithm, the posterior-predictive reading of the D/E priors, and the technical distinction between VMP path updates and the filtering-style treatment used in the reference routine [2].

4.3 Structural Restrictions in the Full RGM Hierarchy

With states, paths, transition tensors, and the D/E hierarchical priors in place, the structural restriction behind Figure 3 of Friston et al. [1] can be stated without introducing any new variables. Figure 2 of Friston et al. [1] allows a more general factor graph in which a child may have several parents. An RGM uses a narrower architecture:

1. The hierarchy is recursive across scales. Each level is built from the same kind of discrete temporal model: hidden-state factors, path factors, and path-conditioned transitions. A higher level is a coarse-grained model of lower-level groups rather than an arbitrary extra graph over them.
2. A higher state owns a lower-level group. It generates a lower segment’s initial states through D and initial paths through E ; the segment then unfolds under its own transition tensor B .
3. Vertical groups do not overlap. A lower-level initial state or path has one parent factor at the level above. A parent may generate several lower-level children, but those children are not shared with sibling higher-level factors.
4. Cross-group dependence is pushed upward. Lower-level variables can have strong local dependence within a group because they share a higher cause and participate in lower-level dynamics. Dependencies between groups are represented at coarser levels rather than by dense shared-child couplings at every vertical link.
5. Temporal coarse graining separates timescales. A higher state generates a finite lower-level trajectory by setting its initial condition and path. Higher states therefore change only after a block of lower-level transitions, so deeper levels encode sequences of sequences.

The one-parent condition in the third item is what makes the hierarchical mappings low dimensional. A general multi-parent D or E mapping would have parent dimensions for co-parents. In the RGM partition, each lower-level initial state and path receives its vertical empirical prior from one higher-level factor, so each such link can be represented by a matrix.

It also explains the conditional-independence claim in Friston et al. [1]. Because lower-level children are not shared by sibling higher-level factors, the Markov blanket of one factor does not acquire those siblings through common children. Conditional on the lower-level initial states and paths that pass evidence upward, latent factors at a level are separated from one another. The

architecture can therefore model rich local compositions while moving broader dependencies to higher scales.

4.4 Control Paths

The paths above were latent dynamical modes: they were inferred from transition evidence and, in the hierarchical model, could receive priors from the level above. Friston et al. [1] also consider control paths. A control path is a path that can be selected through action. For such paths, the prior is not the fixed-path persistence prior

$$P(u_\tau = h \mid u_{\tau-1} = h', J) = J_{hh'}, \quad J = I.$$

Instead, Friston et al. [1] place a direct prior over candidate control paths using expected free energy:

$$P(u_\tau = h) = \pi_G(h), \quad \pi_G(h) := \text{norm}_h(\pi_h^u e^{-G_h}).$$

Here π^u is a baseline prior over control paths and G_h scores the predicted future under candidate path h . Lower expected free energy makes that path more probable. The preferences, ambiguity, and epistemic terms that determine G_h are planning quantities, so Section 5 returns to their reference-algorithm use in detail. The local path update keeps the same form as before,

$$\hat{u}_{\tau-1}^f = \sigma\left(m_{\uparrow B}^f + m_{\text{prior}}^f\right),$$

but planning now supplies the prior message:

$$m_{\text{prior}}^f = \ell\left(\pi_G^f\right).$$

For one controllable factor, π_G^f is just the expected-free-energy prior over that factor's candidate paths. With several controllable factors, expected free energy is evaluated for joint policies and then marginalized back down to factorwise control-path priors. That policy-level construction is deferred to the reference planning account in Section 5.

Up to the normalization absorbed by the softmax, the single-factor update can therefore be read as

$$q(u_{\tau-1}) = \sigma\left(\underbrace{m_{\uparrow B}}_{\text{how well this path explains the transition}} + \underbrace{\ell(\pi^u)}_{\text{baseline prior}} - \underbrace{G}_{\text{planning bias}}\right).$$

Thus the transition message asks which path explains the inferred state change, while the planning message favours controllable paths whose predicted consequences have low expected free energy.

5 Inference and Planning: Fixed Points and Reference Implementation

5.1 Fixed-Point Equations Versus the Reference Implementation

The preceding sections introduced the variables, factors, and message-passing updates used in static and temporal RGMs. This section turns to inference and planning as they are carried out in practice. Its main aim is to relate the fixed-point equations presented by Friston et al. [1] to the procedural reference implementation in the SPM MATLAB routine `toolbox/DEM/spm_MDP_VB_XXX.m` [2]. These two accounts are closely related, but they do not always coincide step by step.

The fixed-point account makes the local variational message structure explicit: it specifies which variables exchange messages and what information those messages carry. The reference implementation, by contrast, shows how inference, planning, replay, and parent-child recursion are realised procedurally in code. Both accounts are built around the same basic generative model and many of the same sufficient statistics, but they sometimes organise the updates differently. When such differences matter, this section distinguishes the conceptual message-passing interpretation given by the published equations [1] from the algorithmic procedure used in the reference implementation [2].

5.2 State Inference Given Observations

5.2.1 Fixed-Point Account The earlier sections already derived the state-inference updates, so only the relevant pieces are recalled here. In the simplest static case, an observation updates a hidden-state belief through the likelihood message:

$$q^*(s) = \sigma(\log \pi + m_{\uparrow A}), \quad m_{\uparrow A} = o \odot \varphi(\tilde{a}).$$

The observation contributes evidence for those states that would make the observed outcome likely. In a temporal model, the state at time τ is also constrained by nearby states through the transition model. For an interior time point, the fixed-point update has the form

$$q^*(s_\tau) = \sigma(m_{\uparrow A, \tau} + m_{\rightarrow B, \tau} + m_{\leftarrow B, \tau}).$$

Here $m_{\uparrow A, \tau}$ is the evidence from the current observation, $m_{\rightarrow B, \tau}$ is the message from the previous state, and $m_{\leftarrow B, \tau}$ is the message from the next state.

This is the fixed-point message-passing account: state beliefs are updated by combining observational evidence with temporal consistency. The next subsection explains how the reference implementation [2] uses the same ingredients in a forward filtering procedure.

5.2.2 Reference Implementation The reference implementation [2] updates state beliefs one time step at a time. At time τ , it does two things. First, it predicts the current hidden state from the previous state belief and the transition model. Second, it corrects that prediction using the outcomes observed at the current time. This is a filtering update. It uses observations up to the present time, but not future observations. Future observations can only affect the current state belief later, if a separate smoothing step is run.

We first need a prior belief about the hidden state at time τ before seeing the new outcome. This prior comes from the previous filtered state belief and the transition model. Let $\hat{u}_{\tau-1}^f$ denote the belief over the path that carries state factor f from time $\tau-1$ to time τ . For an uncontrolled factor, this is the inferred posterior belief over its latent path. For a controllable factor whose previous control path has already been selected, this belief is concentrated on the selected path.

The predictive prior is the model's prediction of the current state before the current observation is used. For factor f , it is obtained by marginalising over the previous state, the path, and the transition probabilities:

$$\bar{s}_{\tau,i}^f = \sum_{j,h} \int P(s_\tau^f = i \mid s_{\tau-1}^f = j, u_{\tau-1}^f = h, B^f) q(s_{\tau-1}^f = j) q(u_{\tau-1}^f = h) q(B^f) dB^f.$$

Since

$$P(s_\tau^f = i \mid s_{\tau-1}^f = j, u_{\tau-1}^f = h, B^f) = B_{ijh}^f,$$

and the posterior mean of the transition tensor is

$$\mathbb{E}_{q(B^f)}[B_{ijh}^f] = \mu(\tilde{b}^f)_{ijh},$$

this becomes

$$\bar{s}_{\tau,i}^f = \sum_{j,h} \mu(\tilde{b}^f)_{ijh} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j}^f \hat{u}_{\tau-1,h}^f.$$

This equation averages over uncertainty about the previous state, the path that governed the transition, and the transition probabilities encoded by the posterior mean $\mu(\tilde{b}^f)$.

The same prediction can be written in two stages. First, predict the next state under one path value h :

$$\bar{s}_\tau^{f,h} = (\mu(\tilde{b}^f) \odot e_h) \odot \hat{s}_{\tau-1}^f = \mu(\tilde{b}^f)_{..h} \odot \hat{s}_{\tau-1}^f.$$

Here e_h selects the transition matrix for path h . In words: choose one path-specific transition model and apply it to the previous state belief. Then average those path-specific predictions using $\hat{u}_{\tau-1}^f$ such that

$$\bar{s}_{\tau,i}^f = \sum_h \hat{u}_{\tau-1,h}^f \bar{s}_{\tau,i}^{f,h}$$

This is simply the same as rearranging the sum

$$\bar{s}_{\tau,i}^f = \sum_h \hat{u}_{\tau-1,h}^f \left(\sum_j \mu(\tilde{b}^f)_{ijh} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j}^f \right)$$

At the first time step, there is no previous state belief to propagate. The reference implementation [2] instead uses the effective initial-state prior provided through D :

$$\bar{s}_{0,i}^f = \sum_j \mu(\tilde{d}^f)_{ij} \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{\text{pa}(f)}.$$

Here $\hat{s}_{\tau}^{\text{pa}(f)}$ is the current belief over the parent state at the level above. If there is no higher-level parent, this term is replaced by the model's ordinary initial-state prior.

If the model has several hidden-state factors, the prediction step is performed factor by factor. Each factor is propagated through its own transition model, giving a predictive prior \bar{s}_{τ}^f for that factor. Before the current observation is used, these factorwise priors define a joint predictive prior:

$$\bar{q}_{\tau}(s_{\tau}) = \prod_f \text{Cat}(s_{\tau}^f; \bar{s}_{\tau}^f).$$

This factorisation belongs to the prediction step. It does not mean that the later observation correction must update each factor independently. An outcome modality can depend on several hidden factors at once through its likelihood tensor A^g . For example, the same visual outcome may depend jointly on object identity and location.

The reference implementation [2] therefore uses the factorwise predictions as priors, combines them with the likelihood of the current observation over the relevant joint state configurations, and then returns marginal posterior beliefs for each factor. In short: the transition prediction is factorwise, but the observation correction can use joint evidence across factors.

The prediction is only a prior. Once the outcome at time τ is observed, the reference implementation [2] updates that prior using the likelihood of the observation. Write

$$\mathcal{L}_{\tau}(s_{\tau}) := \prod_g P(o_{\tau}^g \mid s_{\tau}, \tilde{a}^g)$$

for the likelihood of the current outcome vector. This means: for each possible hidden-state configuration s_{τ} , evaluate how likely the observed outcomes are under that state. If there are several outcome modalities, indexed by g , their likelihood terms are multiplied together. When the likelihood is represented by Dirichlet counts, the required probabilities are taken from the expected likelihood matrix $\mu(\tilde{a}^g)$. For one modality,

$$P(o_{\tau}^g = i \mid s_{\tau}, \tilde{a}^g) = \mathbb{E}_{q(A^g)}[A_{i,s_{\tau}}^g] = \mu(\tilde{a}^g)_{i,s_{\tau}} = \frac{\tilde{a}_{i,s_{\tau}}^g}{\sum_{i'} \tilde{a}_{i',s_{\tau}}^g}.$$

The filtered posterior over the current state is then

$$q_{\tau}(s_{\tau}) := \frac{\mathcal{L}_{\tau}(s_{\tau}) \bar{q}_{\tau}(s_{\tau})}{\sum_{s'_{\tau}} \mathcal{L}_{\tau}(s'_{\tau}) \bar{q}_{\tau}(s'_{\tau})}.$$

This is an ordinary Bayes update. The reference implementation [2] then stores a belief for each hidden-state factor. The marginal belief for factor f is

$$\hat{s}_{\tau,i}^f := \sum_{s_{\tau}^{-f}} q_{\tau}(s_{\tau}^f = i, s_{\tau}^{-f}).$$

This equation means: to obtain the belief that factor f is in state i , sum over all possible values of the other state factors. This matters because the observation model may couple factors together. For instance, an observation may depend jointly on location and object identity. The correction step can use that joint dependence before returning separate marginal beliefs for each factor.

The corrected belief \hat{s}_{τ} is used in two later parts of the reference implementation [2]. First, it starts prospective policy evaluation. The reference implementation [2] uses the current corrected belief to predict possible future states and outcomes under candidate policies. Second, it supports retrospective path inference. After the current state belief has been updated, the reference implementation [2] compares $\hat{s}_{\tau-1}$ and \hat{s}_{τ} and asks which path best explains the transition between them. This is only necessary for uncontrollable paths. The next two subsections treat these two uses separately: future-oriented policy evaluation (Policy Evaluation) and backward-looking path inference (Retrospective Path Inference).

5.2.3 Comparison: Fixed-Point Updates and Reference Implementation Filtering The reference filter is related to the fixed-point update, but it is not just the same update with the backward message removed. Even if we ignore the backward message from $s_{\tau+1}$, the two updates combine the same ingredients in different mathematical forms.

For one state factor, the fixed-point VMP update has the form

$$q_{\text{VMP}}(s_{\tau}^f) = \sigma\left(m_{\uparrow A, \tau}^f + m_{\rightarrow B, \tau}^f\right).$$

Equivalently,

$$\log q_{\text{VMP}}(s_{\tau}^f = i) = (m_{\uparrow A, \tau}^f)_i + (m_{\rightarrow B, \tau}^f)_i + \text{const.}$$

For a simple likelihood depending only on factor f , the observation message is

$$(m_{\uparrow A, \tau}^f)_i = \sum_o O_{\tau,o} \varphi(\tilde{a})_{oi},$$

where O_{τ} is the observed outcome vector. If the observation is one-hot at $o = o^*$, this reduces to

$$(m_{\uparrow A, \tau}^f)_i = \varphi(\tilde{a})_{o^*i} = \mathbb{E}[\log A_{o^*i}].$$

The forward transition message is

$$(m_{\rightarrow B, \tau}^f)_i = \sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j}^f \hat{u}_{\tau-1,h}^f \varphi(\tilde{b}^f)_{ijh} = \sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j}^f \hat{u}_{\tau-1,h}^f \mathbb{E}[\log B_{ijh}^f].$$

The reference implementation [2] instead performs a posterior-predictive Bayes update. It first forms the predictive prior

$$\bar{s}_{\tau,i}^f = \sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j}^f \hat{u}_{\tau-1,h}^f \mu(\tilde{b}^f)_{ijh},$$

then corrects this prior using the current observation. In the multi-factor case, this correction is written over the joint state configuration:

$$q_{\text{impl}}(s_\tau) \propto P(o_\tau | s_\tau, \mu(\tilde{a})) \prod_f \bar{s}_{\tau,s_\tau^f}^f.$$

Taking logs gives

$$\log q_{\text{impl}}(s_\tau) = \log P(o_\tau | s_\tau, \mu(\tilde{a})) + \sum_f \log \bar{s}_{\tau,s_\tau^f}^f + \text{const.}$$

For a single factor and a one-hot observation o^* , this becomes

$$\log q_{\text{impl}}(s_\tau^f = i) = \log \mu(\tilde{a})_{o^*i} + \log \left(\sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j}^f \hat{u}_{\tau-1,h}^f \mu(\tilde{b}^f)_{ijh} \right) + \text{const.}$$

So the two updates can be compared directly:

$$\log q_{\text{VMP}}(s_\tau^f = i) = \underbrace{\mathbb{E}[\log A_{o^*i}]}_{\text{expected-log likelihood}} + \underbrace{\sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j}^f \hat{u}_{\tau-1,h}^f \mathbb{E}[\log B_{ijh}^f]}_{\text{expected-log transition message}} + \text{const.},$$

whereas

$$\log q_{\text{impl}}(s_\tau^f = i) = \underbrace{\log \mathbb{E}[A_{o^*i}]}_{\text{log posterior-mean likelihood}} + \underbrace{\log \sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j}^f \hat{u}_{\tau-1,h}^f \mathbb{E}[B_{ijh}^f]}_{\text{log posterior-predictive transition prior}} + \text{const.}$$

The difference is therefore not only the absence of the backward message. The fixed-point update averages log probabilities, while the reference implementation [2] takes logs of posterior-predictive probabilities. In shorthand,

$$\mathbb{E}[\log A] \quad \text{versus} \quad \log \mathbb{E}[A],$$

and

$$\sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_j \hat{u}_h \mathbb{E}[\log B_{ijh}] \quad \text{versus} \quad \log \sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_j \hat{u}_h \mathbb{E}[B_{ijh}].$$

The implication is that the reference implementation [2] is best understood as an online posterior-predictive filter. It predicts the current state using posterior mean transition probabilities, corrects that prediction using the posterior mean likelihood, and then stores the resulting marginal beliefs. The fixed-point equations remain the clean message-passing account of the model, but the reference implementation [2] uses a filtering approximation rather than a literal expected-log VMP update at each time step.

5.3 Policy Evaluation

For policy evaluation, the fixed-point account and the reference implementation [2] use the same basic construction. Starting from the corrected state belief \hat{s}_τ , the model predicts what would happen under each candidate path or joint policy, then scores those predicted consequences with expected free energy. Section 2 introduced expected free energy as a general objective for planning, where

$$\begin{aligned}
 G(u) = & - \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_{Q_u} \left[D_{\text{KL}}(Q(A | s_{\tau+1}, o_{\tau+1}, u) \| Q(A | s_{\tau+1}, u)) \right]}_{\text{novelty}} \\
 & + \underbrace{D_{\text{KL}}(Q(o_{\tau+1} | u) \| P(o_{\tau+1} | c))}_{\text{risk}} \\
 & - \underbrace{\mathbb{E}_{Q_u} \left[\log Q(o_{\tau+1} | s_{\tau+1}, u) \right]}_{\text{ambiguity}}.
 \end{aligned}$$

In the temporal RGM routine, this becomes a path-level or policy-level score. For a candidate path h , write $G_h := G(u = h)$. Once G_h has been evaluated, it shapes the prior over control paths:

$$\pi_G(h) := \text{norm}_h(\pi_h^u e^{-G_h}).$$

Thus paths with lower expected free energy become more probable.

5.3.1 Predicted States and Outcomes Under Candidate Paths To score a path, first predict the next hidden state under that path:

$$Q(s_{\tau+1} | u = h) = \sum_{s_\tau} \int P(s_{\tau+1} | s_\tau, u = h, B) Q(s_\tau) Q(B) dB.$$

This is the current variational prediction of the next state, obtained by averaging over posterior beliefs about s_τ and B . Written explicitly,

$$\hat{s}_{\tau+1}^h = (\mu(\tilde{b}) \odot e_h) \odot \hat{s}_\tau = \mu(\tilde{b})_{\cdot h} \odot \hat{s}_\tau,$$

where e_h selects the path slice used for the candidate prediction. Next, push the predicted next-state distribution through the likelihood. For each modality g ,

$$Q(o_{\tau+1}^g | u = h) = \sum_{s_{\tau+1}} Q(o_{\tau+1}^g | s_{\tau+1}) Q(s_{\tau+1} | u = h),$$

and therefore

$$\hat{o}_{\tau+1}^{g,h} = \mu(\tilde{a}^g) \odot \hat{s}_{\tau+1}^h.$$

So $\hat{o}_{\tau+1}^{g,h}$ is the predicted outcome distribution for modality g under candidate path h .

5.3.2 Risk, Ambiguity, and Terminal-State Preferences The full expected-free-energy expression from Section 2 contains novelty, risk, and ambiguity terms. The one-step score displayed in Figure 1 of Friston et al. [1] focuses on the risk and ambiguity components of expected free energy:

$$G_h = \sum_g \underbrace{\delta_{\tau+1}^{g,h} \odot \left(\ell(\hat{\delta}_{\tau+1}^{g,h}) - \varphi(c^g) \right)}_{\text{risk}} - \underbrace{H_{\text{amb}}^g \odot \hat{s}_{\tau+1}^h}_{\text{ambiguity}}.$$

This should be read as the compact notation used by Friston et al. [1] for scoring predicted outcomes under a candidate path. It is close to the standard risk-plus-ambiguity form,

$$G_h \approx D_{\text{KL}}\left(Q(o_{\tau+1} | u = h) \| p_{\text{pref}}(o_{\tau+1})\right) + \mathbb{E}_{Q(s_{\tau+1}|u=h)} \left[H(Q(o_{\tau+1} | s_{\tau+1})) \right],$$

with sign conventions depending on whether the score is written as free energy to minimise or utility to maximise. For a single modality, the literal risk term is

$$D_{\text{KL}}(Q(o_{\tau+1} | u) \| p_{\text{pref}}(o_{\tau+1})) = \sum_o Q(o_{\tau+1} = o | u) \log \frac{Q(o_{\tau+1} = o | u)}{p_{\text{pref}}(o)}.$$

If preferences are represented by Dirichlet counts c , the posterior-mean preferred-outcome distribution is

$$p_{\text{pref}}(o = j) = \mu(c)_j.$$

A literal posterior-predictive KL therefore uses $\log \mu(c)_j$. Figure 1 of Friston et al. [1] instead writes the preference term with

$$\varphi(c)_j = \mathbb{E}[\log C_j].$$

This is the same expected-log versus log-mean distinction seen earlier:

$$\varphi(c)_j = \mathbb{E}[\log C_j], \quad \log \mu(c)_j = \log \mathbb{E}[C_j].$$

The same issue appears in the ambiguity term. The literal posterior-predictive ambiguity for a fixed state uses

$$Q(o = i | s = j) = \mu(\tilde{a})_{ij},$$

and therefore contains terms such as

$$- \sum_i \mu(\tilde{a})_{ij} \log \mu(\tilde{a})_{ij}.$$

Figure 1 of Friston et al. [1] instead defines

$$H_{\text{amb}}^g = \mathbf{1} \odot (\mu(\tilde{a}^g) \times \varphi(\tilde{a}^g)),$$

which uses $\varphi(\tilde{a}) = \mathbb{E}[\log A]$ rather than $\log \mu(\tilde{a}) = \log \mathbb{E}[A]$.

The reference implementation [2] is closer to the posterior-predictive risk and ambiguity form. It predicts outcomes using the posterior mean likelihood,

$$\hat{o}_{\tau+1}^{g,h} = \mu(\tilde{a}^g) \odot \hat{s}_{\tau+1}^h,$$

then evaluates risk using predicted outcome probabilities and preferences, and ambiguity using the entropy of the posterior-mean likelihood columns. Novelty terms associated with parameter uncertainty are handled separately. Thus Figure 1 of Friston et al. [1] is best read as a compact expected-log shorthand, while the reference implementation [2] uses a posterior-predictive policy score for the risk and ambiguity components.

The expected-free-energy score can also include preferences over terminal hidden states. For factor f , write

$$P(s_T^f | H^f) = \text{Cat}(H^f).$$

Here H^f is a preference distribution in latent-state space, not the entropy functional $H(\cdot)$. Under a candidate path $u = h$, the corresponding state-risk contribution is

$$G_h^{\text{state}} = \sum_f D_{\text{KL}}[Q(s_T^f | u_\tau = h) \| H^f].$$

Outcome preferences $p_{\text{pref}}(o)$ and terminal-state preferences H^f are not redundant: the former specify what the agent wants to see, while the latter specify which latent configurations it wants to reach.

5.3.3 From Joint Policies to Factorwise Path Priors Once G_h has been computed for each path h , it enters the path prior through

$$\pi_G(h) := \text{norm}_h(\pi_h^u e^{-G_h}).$$

The predictive expectation is already inside G_h . Therefore the local path update treats the resulting score as a prior message rather than taking another expectation over future variables:

$$\mathbb{E}_{q_{-u}}[G_h] = G_h.$$

Equivalently,

$$\mathbb{E}_{q_{-u}}[\log P(u = h)] = \log \pi_h^u - G_h + \text{const}.$$

The direct formula over path labels is the single-control-path presentation. With several controllable factors, planning scores joint assignments of their control paths. Let \mathcal{U} denote the controllable factors. A policy table V lists the admissible assignments,

$$V_k = (V_{k,f})_{f \in \mathcal{U}},$$

so row V_k says that policy k assigns factor f the path value

$$u_\tau^f = V_{k,f}.$$

That row selects the appropriate transition slice for each controllable factor:

$$P(s_{\tau+1}^f | s_{\tau}^f, V_k) = P(s_{\tau+1}^f | s_{\tau}^f, u_{\tau}^f = V_{k,f}).$$

Expected free energy therefore yields a distribution over policies,

$$q(k) \propto \pi_0(k) e^{-G(k)},$$

and each controllable factor receives the marginal prior over its own path:

$$\pi_G^f(h) = \sum_k q(k) \mathbf{1}[V_{k,f} = h].$$

The single-factor case is the degenerate case in which policy labels and path labels coincide. In the multi-factor case, planning evaluates coordinated joint futures, whereas each factorwise path update needs a prior over that factor's own path. Uncontrolled factors are not selected by V : if one has a single path its transition is fixed, while multiple uncontrolled paths are inferred and predictions average over their current path belief.

So u is not directly conditioned on c in the ordinary sense. Rather, c shapes G , and G in turn shapes the path prior π_G . Friston et al. [1] compress these distinctions considerably, so it is helpful to keep the dependence chain explicit.

The reason for scoring joint policies is that expected free energy is a score of predicted consequences, not just isolated factor transitions. The transition model may factor by hidden-state factor,

$$P(s_{\tau+1} | s_{\tau}, V_k) = \prod_f P(s_{\tau+1}^f | s_{\tau}^f, u_{\tau}^f = V_{k,f}),$$

but the predicted outcomes need not factor in the same way. An outcome modality can depend on a joint state configuration,

$$P(o_{\tau+1}^g | s_{\tau+1}) = P(o_{\tau+1}^g | s_{\tau+1}^1, s_{\tau+1}^2, \dots).$$

In that case, the value of choosing a path for one factor can depend on which paths are chosen for the other factors, because their combined future state determines the predicted outcome and therefore the risk, ambiguity, and preference terms. If the model were fully separable, with each factor generating only its own independent outcomes and preferences, factorwise policy scoring would be enough. The RGM routine keeps the more general joint-policy evaluation, then marginalizes the resulting policy posterior back into factorwise path priors for the local path updates.

5.4 Retrospective Path Inference

Prospective policy evaluation asks what a future path or joint policy would imply. Retrospective path inference asks the complementary question: after the model has inferred $\hat{s}_{\tau-1}$ and \hat{s}_{τ} , which path best explains that transition?

5.4.1 Fixed-Point Account In the Figure 2 fixed-point account of Friston et al. [1], the posterior over the previous path combines transition evidence with a prior message:

$$\hat{u}_{\tau-1} = \sigma(m_{\uparrow B} + m_{\text{prior}}).$$

For a candidate path h , the transition evidence is an expected-log message:

$$m_{\uparrow B}(h) = \mathbb{E}[\log P(s_{\tau} | s_{\tau-1}, u_{\tau-1} = h, B)].$$

Expanding this under the posterior beliefs over the two neighbouring states gives

$$m_{\uparrow B}(h) = \sum_{i,j} \hat{s}_{\tau,i} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j} \mathbb{E}[\log B_{ijh}] = \sum_{i,j} \hat{s}_{\tau,i} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j} \varphi(\tilde{b})_{ijh}.$$

Thus, in the fixed-point account, a path is inferred from how well its transition slice explains the inferred movement from $s_{\tau-1}$ to s_{τ} , using expected log transition probabilities.

5.4.2 Reference Implementation The reference implementation [2] uses the same retrospective idea, but it scores each path with a posterior-predictive transition likelihood. After the state beliefs have been corrected, it evaluates each candidate path by asking how likely that path makes the inferred transition:

$$LL(h) = \log \left(\sum_{i,j} \hat{s}_{\tau,i} \mu(\tilde{b})_{ijh} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j} \right).$$

The path posterior is then

$$\hat{u}_{\tau-1} = \sigma(LL + m_{\text{prior}}).$$

The prior message depends on the kind of path. For a fixed or persistent path, the prior carries forward the previous path belief: $m_{\text{prior}} = \log \hat{u}_{\tau-2}$. For a controllable path, the prior is shaped by policy evaluation: $m_{\text{prior}} = \ell(\pi_G)$.

5.4.3 Comparison: Expected-Log Evidence Versus Predictive Likelihood Both the fixed-point account and the reference implementation [2] combine transition evidence with a prior over paths. The prior has the same conceptual role in each account, but its source depends on which path is being inferred. For the initial path of a lower-level segment, the prior is supplied by the hierarchical E mapping, $m_{\text{prior}} = m_{\downarrow E}^f$. For fixed or uncontrolled paths later in the segment, the prior carries forward the previous path belief, $m_{\text{prior}} = \log \hat{u}_{\tau-2}^f$. For controllable paths, it is supplied by policy evaluation, $m_{\text{prior}} = \ell(\pi_G^f)$. The reference implementation [2] represents these cases through the path prior already stored for the transition being evaluated. The main difference is therefore not the prior term, but the transition-evidence term.

In the fixed-point account, the evidence for path h is an expected-log transition message:

$$m_{\uparrow B}(h) = \sum_{i,j} \hat{s}_{\tau,i} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j} \mathbb{E}[\log B_{ijh}].$$

In the reference implementation [2], the evidence for path h is instead the log posterior-predictive probability of the inferred transition:

$$LL(h) = \log \left(\sum_{i,j} \hat{s}_{\tau,i} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j} \mathbb{E}[B_{ijh}] \right).$$

So the distinction mirrors the state-inference comparison in Section 5.2. The fixed-point message averages log transition probabilities, whereas the reference implementation [2] takes the log of an averaged transition probability:

$$\sum_{i,j} \hat{s}_{\tau,i} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j} \mathbb{E}[\log B_{ijh}] \quad \text{versus} \quad \log \left(\sum_{i,j} \hat{s}_{\tau,i} \hat{s}_{\tau-1,j} \mathbb{E}[B_{ijh}] \right).$$

These expressions become close when the neighbouring state beliefs are sharp and the posterior over B is highly concentrated. In that case, there is little uncertainty about which transition occurred or about the transition probabilities themselves. More generally, the reference implementation [2] should be read as a posterior-predictive path filter: it asks which path makes the inferred transition most likely under the posterior mean transition model. The fixed-point equation remains the clean VMP message-passing account, but the reference routine uses a log predictive likelihood for retrospective path inference.

5.5 Recursive Parent-Child Inference

The reference implementation [2] is recursive: a higher-level state provides empirical priors for a lower-level segment, and the lower-level segment returns posterior summaries that become observations for the higher level. This is the algorithmic version of the RGM idea that higher states contextualise lower-level trajectories.

5.5.1 Fixed-Point Account Suppose a higher-level state $s_{\tau}^{(n+1)}$ contextualises a lower-level segment at level n . The higher level predicts how the lower segment should begin by placing priors over its initial state and initial path:

$$P(s_0^{(n),f} \mid s_{\tau}^{(n+1)}, D^f), \quad P(u_0^{(n),f} \mid s_{\tau}^{(n+1)}, E^f).$$

Read downward, D and E therefore provide empirical priors over the child segment's initial conditions.

In exact mean-field VMP, these descending messages are expected-log messages. For a one-parent mapping, the state message would be

$$m_{\downarrow D}^f(i) = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \mathbb{E}[\log D_{ij}^f] = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \varphi(\tilde{d}^f)_{ij},$$

and the analogous path message would be

$$m_{\downarrow E}^f(h) = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \mathbb{E}[\log E_{hj}^f] = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \varphi(\tilde{e}^f)_{hj}.$$

5.5.2 Reference Implementation The reference implementation [2] uses a posterior-predictive version of the same idea. Instead of passing an expected-log message, it forms an ordinary prior distribution over the child’s initial state:

$$D_{\text{parent}}^f(i) = \sum_j \mu(\tilde{d}^f)_{ij} \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)}.$$

Likewise, the parent-induced prior over the child’s initial path is

$$E_{\text{parent}}^f(h) = \sum_j \mu(\tilde{e}^f)_{hj} \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)}.$$

The child may also already have local priors before the parent supplies context. Here D_{local}^f means the child model’s current initial-state prior before the parent-induced prior is applied. It is not a new theoretical object; it is the prior already present in the child. Depending on the situation, it may be a default prior, such as a uniform prior, or a continuity prior from the previous child segment. When the child has already been inverted, a natural continuity prior is obtained by propagating the child’s previous terminal state posterior through its own transition model:

$$D_{\text{local}}^f(i) = \sum_{j,h} \mu(\tilde{b}^f)_{ijh} \hat{s}_{T,j}^{(n),f} \hat{u}_{T-1,h}^{(n),f}.$$

This says: given where the previous child segment ended, predict where the next child segment should begin.

Similarly, E_{local}^f denotes the child’s current initial-path prior before parent context is applied. It may be a default path prior, or it may be carried forward from the previous child path posterior.

The effective priors used to initialise the child segment are then formed by multiplying the local and parent-induced priors and normalising:

$$D_{\text{eff}}^f(i) = \frac{D_{\text{local}}^f(i) D_{\text{parent}}^f(i)}{\sum_{i'} D_{\text{local}}^f(i') D_{\text{parent}}^f(i')},$$

and

$$E_{\text{eff}}^f(h) = \frac{E_{\text{local}}^f(h) E_{\text{parent}}^f(h)}{\sum_{h'} E_{\text{local}}^f(h') E_{\text{parent}}^f(h')}.$$

So the parent does not replace the child’s local priors. It contextualises them.

Information also travels upward. After the child segment has been inverted, the reference recursion returns posterior summaries from the lower level. In the

notation used here, these are the child’s initial-state posterior and a path posterior summary:

$$\hat{s}_0^{(n),f}, \quad \hat{u}_{T-1}^{(n),f}.$$

These summaries become state-channel and path-channel observations for the parent level. This creates a small asymmetry: read downward, E predicts the child’s initial path; read upward, the path summary may be taken from the end of the child inversion. For persistent paths, these can coincide in practice.

5.5.3 Comparison: Expected-Log Messages Versus Posterior-Predictive Recursion There are two directions to compare: the downward message from parent to child, and the upward evidence from child back to parent.

For the downward direction, exact VMP would initialise the child state with an expected-log message. For a one-parent D mapping,

$$\log q_{\text{VMP}}(s_0^{(n),f} = i) = m_{\downarrow D}^f(i) + \text{other child messages} + \text{const},$$

where

$$m_{\downarrow D}^f(i) = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \mathbb{E}[\log D_{ij}^f] = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \varphi(\tilde{d}^f)_{ij}.$$

The analogous path message is

$$m_{\downarrow E}^f(h) = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \mathbb{E}[\log E_{hj}^f] = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \varphi(\tilde{e}^f)_{hj}.$$

The reference implementation [2] instead forms posterior-predictive empirical priors. For the child state,

$$D_{\text{parent}}^f(i) = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \mathbb{E}[D_{ij}^f] = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \mu(\tilde{d}^f)_{ij}.$$

and combines this with the child’s already-present local prior:

$$D_{\text{eff}}^f(i) \propto D_{\text{local}}^f(i) D_{\text{parent}}^f(i).$$

Thus the implemented child-state update uses

$$\log q_{\text{impl}}(s_0^{(n),f} = i) = \log D_{\text{eff}}^f(i) + \text{other child messages} + \text{const}.$$

The same construction applies to the child path:

$$E_{\text{parent}}^f(h) = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \mu(\tilde{e}^f)_{hj}, \quad E_{\text{eff}}^f(h) \propto E_{\text{local}}^f(h) E_{\text{parent}}^f(h),$$

so that

$$\log q_{\text{impl}}(u_0^{(n),f} = h) = \log E_{\text{eff}}^f(h) + \text{other child messages} + \text{const}.$$

Comparing the two child-state updates is clearest in log space. If the child carries temporal continuity from the previous segment, then an exact VMP-style update would have the form

$$\log q_{\text{VMP}}(s_0^{(n),f} = i) = m_{\rightarrow B, \text{local}}^f(i) + m_{\downarrow D}^f(i) + \text{other child messages} + \text{const.}$$

Here the local forward-transition message is

$$m_{\rightarrow B, \text{local}}^f(i) = \sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_{T,j}^{(n),f} \hat{u}_{T-1,h}^{(n),f} \mathbb{E}[\log B_{ijh}^f],$$

and the descending parent message is

$$m_{\downarrow D}^f(i) = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \mathbb{E}[\log D_{ij}^f].$$

The reference implementation [2] instead uses posterior-predictive priors. Its child-state update has the form

$$\log q_{\text{impl}}(s_0^{(n),f} = i) = \log D_{\text{local}}^f(i) + \log D_{\text{parent}}^f(i) + \text{other child messages} + \text{const.},$$

where the normalisation of $D_{\text{eff}}^f \propto D_{\text{local}}^f D_{\text{parent}}^f$ has been absorbed into the constant. When D_{local}^f is a continuity prior from the previous child segment,

$$D_{\text{local}}^f(i) = \sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_{T,j}^{(n),f} \hat{u}_{T-1,h}^{(n),f} \mathbb{E}[B_{ijh}^f],$$

so

$$\log D_{\text{local}}^f(i) = \log \left(\sum_{j,h} \hat{s}_{T,j}^{(n),f} \hat{u}_{T-1,h}^{(n),f} \mathbb{E}[B_{ijh}^f] \right).$$

This is the implementation-side analogue of the local forward B message. The difference is the same as before: VMP averages log transition probabilities, whereas the reference implementation [2] takes the log of a posterior-predictive transition probability.

The parent-induced term differs in the same way:

$$m_{\downarrow D}^f(i) = \sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \mathbb{E}[\log D_{ij}^f],$$

whereas

$$\log D_{\text{parent}}^f(i) = \log \left(\sum_j \hat{s}_{\tau,j}^{(n+1)} \mathbb{E}[D_{ij}^f] \right).$$

Thus the reference implementation [2] combines two posterior-predictive priors: a local prior from the child's own dynamics, when available, and a parent-induced empirical prior from D . The same comparison applies to E : exact VMP uses

expected-log E messages, while the reference implementation [2] uses $\log E_{\text{eff}}^f(h)$, combining the child’s local path prior with a posterior-predictive parent prior.

For the upward direction, the object being updated is the parent state. The child segment has already been inverted, so its posterior summaries now provide evidence about which parent state could have generated that child segment.

In the VMP account, the parent receives expected-log evidence from each child. If child d returns an initial-state summary $\hat{s}_0^{(n),d}$, then its upward D message to parent state j is

$$m_{\uparrow D}^d(j) = \sum_i \hat{s}_{0,i}^{(n),d} \mathbb{E}[\log D_{ij}^d] = \sum_i \hat{s}_{0,i}^{(n),d} \varphi(\tilde{d}^d)_{ij}.$$

Likewise, if child e returns a path summary, the upward E message is

$$m_{\uparrow E}^e(j) = \sum_h \hat{u}_h^{(n),e} \mathbb{E}[\log E_{hj}^e] = \sum_h \hat{u}_h^{(n),e} \varphi(\tilde{e}^e)_{hj}.$$

Here $\hat{u}^{(n),e}$ denotes the path summary sent upward by the child. In the reference recursion this may be taken from the final transition of the child inversion, $\hat{u}_{T-1}^{(n),e}$, rather than the initial path belief.

The fixed-point parent posterior therefore has the form

$$\begin{aligned} \log q_{\text{VMP}}(s_\tau^{(n+1)} = j) &= \sum_d \sum_i \hat{s}_{0,i}^{(n),d} \mathbb{E}[\log D_{ij}^d] + \sum_e \sum_h \hat{u}_h^{(n),e} \mathbb{E}[\log E_{hj}^e] \\ &\quad + \text{other parent messages} + \text{const.} \end{aligned}$$

In the reference implementation [2], the child summaries are treated as observations for the parent. The parent state j is scored by asking how likely those child summaries are under the posterior mean D and E mappings:

$$\begin{aligned} \log q_{\text{impl}}(s_\tau^{(n+1)} = j) &= \sum_d \log P(\hat{s}_0^{(n),d} \mid s_\tau^{(n+1)} = j, \mu(\tilde{d}^d)) + \sum_e \log P(\hat{u}_{T-1}^{(n),e} \mid s_\tau^{(n+1)} = j, \mu(\tilde{e}^e)) \\ &\quad + \text{other parent messages} + \text{const.} \end{aligned}$$

For soft categorical summaries, this becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \log q_{\text{impl}}(s_\tau^{(n+1)} = j) &= \sum_d \log \left(\sum_i \hat{s}_{0,i}^{(n),d} \mu(\tilde{d}^d)_{ij} \right) + \sum_e \log \left(\sum_h \hat{u}_{T-1,h}^{(n),e} \mu(\tilde{e}^e)_{hj} \right) \\ &\quad + \text{other parent messages} + \text{const.} \end{aligned}$$

The comparison is therefore direct. For a child-state summary, VMP contributes

$$\sum_i \hat{s}_{0,i}^{(n),d} \mathbb{E}[\log D_{ij}^d],$$

whereas the reference implementation [2] contributes

$$\log \left(\sum_i \hat{s}_{0,i}^{(n),d} \mathbb{E}[D_{ij}^d] \right).$$

Similarly, for a child-path summary, VMP contributes

$$\sum_h \hat{u}_h^{(n),e} \mathbb{E}[\log E_{hj}^e],$$

whereas the reference implementation [2] contributes

$$\log \left(\sum_h \hat{u}_{T-1,h}^{(n),e} \mathbb{E}[E_{hj}^e] \right).$$

So the upward comparison is slightly simpler than the downward one. Downward, the reference implementation [2] first builds an empirical prior and multiplies it into the child’s local prior. Upward, the reference implementation [2] treats the child’s posterior summaries as soft observations and evaluates their likelihood under the posterior mean mappings. In both directions, however, the same general distinction appears: the fixed-point account uses expected-log messages, while the reference implementation [2] uses log posterior-predictive quantities. When the child summaries are one-hot, the soft-observation likelihood reduces to the likelihood of the selected child state or path; when they are genuinely soft, the reference implementation [2] takes the log after averaging over the possible child states or paths.

5.6 Reference Implementation: Optional Replay and Smoothing

The temporal updates described so far run forward through the episode. At each step τ , state and path beliefs are formed from outcomes that have already been seen, so the agent holds filtering-style posteriors

$$q(s_\tau | o_{0:\tau}), \quad q(u_\tau | o_{0:\tau}).$$

Here u_τ denotes the path for the transition $s_\tau \rightarrow s_{\tau+1}$, so path indices run over $0 \leq \tau < T$. This is enough for online inference and online action selection.

Once the episode is over, the agent can optionally run a backward smoothing pass that revisits each τ with all outcomes in hand. The filtering posterior is replaced by the smoothed posterior

$$q(s_\tau | o_{0:T}), \quad q(u_\tau | o_{0:T}),$$

which can shift earlier beliefs in light of how the episode actually played out. This is the natural interpretation of the optional replay pass described in Friston et al. [1] and implemented in the reference routine [2].

The controlled-versus-uncontrolled distinction changes the shape of this pass. For an uncontrolled persistent path, the smoothed path posterior collapses to a single belief shared across the epoch:

$$\hat{u}_\tau^f \leftarrow \hat{u}_{T-1}^f \quad (\text{uncontrolled persistent factor } f).$$

For a controlled path, by contrast, u_τ^f was chosen through expected-free-energy-based policy selection. The smoothing pass does not flatten controlled paths into a single end-of-episode belief; their values remain tied to the policy that was enacted while state beliefs are re-smoothed against the realised outcome sequence.

6 Parameter Learning and Active Learning

Up to this point, the story has been: infer latent states and paths, and update parameters by adding expected counts. Active learning adds one more layer: whether a candidate count update should be admitted is itself treated as a decision scored by expected free energy.

Here, active learning does not mean updating the likelihood counts every time a new observation is seen. Instead, the idea is:

1. compute the candidate count update;
2. treat whether to apply that update as a binary action;
3. choose that action using expected free energy.

So active learning here means selective updating of the Dirichlet counts. This is exactly how Friston et al. [1] introduce active learning: the update itself is treated as something that may or may not be admitted, depending on its expected free energy.

6.1 Conjugate Expected-Count Learning

Before an update can be accepted or rejected, the model needs the ordinary conjugate update that would be available without active learning. For a categorical factor with Dirichlet parameters, the sufficient statistic is an expected count: observed outcomes contribute one-hot outcome mass and uncertain latent parents contribute posterior belief mass.

The earlier RGM derivations already gave the main count increments. Collected together, the ordinary updates have the form

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{likelihood counts} \quad & \tilde{a}^g \leftarrow \tilde{a}^g + o_\tau^g \otimes_{i \in pa(g)} \hat{s}_\tau^i, & \text{state-outcome co-occurrences,} \\
 \text{transition counts} \quad & \tilde{b}^f \leftarrow \tilde{b}^f + \hat{s}_\tau^f \otimes \hat{s}_{\tau-1}^f \otimes \hat{u}_{\tau-1}^f, & \text{state-path transitions,} \\
 \text{initial-state counts} \quad & \tilde{d}^f \leftarrow \tilde{d}^f + \hat{s}_0^f \otimes_{i \in pa(f)} \hat{s}^i, & \text{higher-state to lower-state links,} \\
 \text{initial-path counts} \quad & \tilde{e}^f \leftarrow \tilde{e}^f + \hat{u}_0^f \otimes_{i \in pa(f)} \hat{s}^i, & \text{higher-state to lower-path links.}
 \end{aligned}$$

Active learning does not change the candidate expected counts. It changes whether selected candidate updates are admitted, beginning with the likelihood update used in Friston et al. [1].

6.2 Fixed-Point Account: Active Learning as Gated Likelihood Updating

6.2.1 Candidate Likelihood Update From Figure 2A of Friston et al. [1], the ordinary likelihood update is

$$\tilde{a} \leftarrow \tilde{a} + o_\tau \otimes_{i \in pa} \hat{s}_\tau^i.$$

The active-learning section rewrites the increment as

$$\Delta a = o_\tau \otimes_{i \in pa} \hat{s}_\tau^i.$$

Nothing active has happened yet. This is only the update that could be made. So active learning does not change the form of the candidate Dirichlet update. The only question is whether that increment will actually be incorporated.

6.2.2 Update Gates Friston et al. [1] then define two possible update actions. To avoid overloading the path variable u , write these as an update gate r :

- $r = 0$: do not update;
- $r = 1$: update.

So the corresponding parameter values are

$$\tilde{a}_{\tau+1} \mid r = 0 = \tilde{a}_\tau, \quad \tilde{a}_{\tau+1} \mid r = 1 = \tilde{a}_\tau + \Delta a.$$

This is the key active-learning move: the update itself is treated as something that can be selected or rejected.

A small notational caveat is worth flagging here. Friston et al. [1] write these update actions as u_0 and u_1 , even though u denotes a path or policy variable elsewhere. Here we use r for the update gate so this internal learning decision is not confused with a path.

6.2.3 Expected Free Energy Over Update Gates The posterior probability of the two update actions is written as

$$q(r) = \sigma(-\beta G(\tilde{a}_{\tau+1} \mid r)).$$

This uses exactly the same idea as policy selection elsewhere in Friston et al. [1]: lower expected free energy implies higher probability. The precision is written as β here to distinguish the precision over internal learning updates from the planning precision α used for external paths or policies.

Here, however, the “policy” is not an external action sequence. It is the internal choice between

- keeping the current parameter tensor;
- replacing it with the updated one.

So active learning means that parameter updates are gated by expected free energy. Friston et al. [1] write

$$\begin{aligned} G(a) &= -\mathbb{E}_{Q_a} \left[D_{\text{KL}}(Q(s, o | a) \| Q(s | a) P(o | a)) \right] - \mathbb{E}_{Q_a} [\log P(o | c)] \\ &= -I(O; S | a) - \mathbb{E}_{Q_a} [\log P(o | c)]. \end{aligned}$$

This has two components:

- an epistemic term;
- a pragmatic term, encoding preferences or costs.

Here, the epistemic term is written as the mutual information between hidden states and outcomes under the candidate parameter tensor a . So an update is favored when it is expected to make the likelihood mapping more informative, while also respecting any preference term encoded by c .

6.2.4 The Predictive Joint Q_a In the active-learning section, Q_a should be read as the joint distribution over outcomes and hidden states induced by a given candidate count tensor a . Here a is used as a generic argument of $G(a)$; in the update equations above, the concrete candidates are \tilde{a}_τ and $\tilde{a}_\tau + \Delta a$:

$$Q_a(o, s) \equiv P(o, s | a).$$

So here Q_a is not the posterior over the random variable a . It is the predictive joint distribution encoded by a particular candidate value of a .

That distinction matters, because otherwise it is easy to misread the expected free energy as being taken over uncertainty about a . That is not what is happening here. Friston et al. [1] score a candidate parameter tensor by looking at the joint distribution over outcomes and causes that it induces.

6.2.5 Globally Normalising the Count Tensor Friston et al. [1] define

$$\bar{a} = \frac{a}{\Sigma(a)},$$

where $\Sigma(a)$ is the sum of all entries of the tensor.

This is not the usual column-normalization used to obtain the expected likelihood matrix from Dirichlet counts. Normally, if a is the concentration matrix for a likelihood A , each column is normalized separately. Here, instead, Friston et al. [1] globally normalize the whole tensor so that

$$\sum_{o,s} \bar{a}_{os} = 1.$$

This is a temporary reinterpretation of the count tensor as a joint probability table over (o, s) . For a matrix a , we can read

$$\bar{a}_{ij} = P(o = i, s = j | a).$$

Then the contractions

$$\mathbf{1} \odot \bar{a} \quad \text{and} \quad \bar{a} \odot \mathbf{1}$$

give the marginals $P(s | a)$ and $P(o | a)$, respectively, up to the indexing convention used in Friston et al. [1].

This reinterpretation is what makes the mutual-information expression meaningful: once \bar{a} is treated as a joint distribution over outcomes and states, one can form marginals and compute

$$I(O; S | a).$$

6.2.6 Mutual Information in Tensor Form With \bar{a} treated as a joint distribution, the epistemic term is just the usual mutual-information identity

$$I(O; S | a) = H(O | a) + H(S | a) - H(O, S | a),$$

so

$$-I(O; S | a) = -H(O | a) - H(S | a) + H(O, S | a).$$

Writing those entropies out explicitly gives

$$\begin{aligned} -I(O; S | a) &= \sum_o P(o | a) \log P(o | a) + \sum_s P(s | a) \log P(s | a) \\ &\quad - \sum_{o,s} P(o, s | a) \log P(o, s | a). \end{aligned}$$

This is what Friston et al. [1] write in tensor notation as

$$(\mathbf{1} \odot \bar{a}) \odot \ell(\mathbf{1} \odot \bar{a}) + (\bar{a} \odot \mathbf{1}) \odot \ell(\bar{a} \odot \mathbf{1}) - \mathbf{1} \odot (\bar{a} \times \ell(\bar{a})) \odot \mathbf{1},$$

together with the preference term involving c .

So the dense tensor expression is not conceptually new. It is just the standard mutual-information formula written using the contraction notation used in Friston et al. [1].

6.2.7 Preference Term The full expected free energy also includes the preference term

$$-\mathbb{E}_{Q_a}[\log P(o | c)].$$

Because this term depends only on o , it can equivalently be written as an expectation under the outcome marginal $P(o | a)$. So it penalizes candidate updates that would lead to outcomes that are dispreferred under c .

As elsewhere in Friston et al. [1], one should keep in mind the same caveat about preferred outcomes: the notation is compact, but the exact form depends on how one reads $P(o | c)$ from the Dirichlet parameters c .

6.2.8 Bayesian Model Average Over Update Gates Once the two update gates have probabilities $q(r = 0)$ and $q(r = 1)$, Friston et al. [1] average over the two possible futures for the parameter tensor:

$$\mathbb{E}_Q[\tilde{a}_{\tau+1}^g] = q(r = 0) \mathbb{E}_Q[\tilde{a}_{\tau+1}^g \mid r = 0] + q(r = 1) \mathbb{E}_Q[\tilde{a}_{\tau+1}^g \mid r = 1].$$

Substituting the two cases gives

$$\tilde{a}_{\tau+1}^g = q(r = 0) \tilde{a}_\tau^g + q(r = 1) (\tilde{a}_\tau^g + \Delta a_\tau^g).$$

Since

$$q(r = 0) + q(r = 1) = 1,$$

this simplifies to

$$\tilde{a}_{\tau+1}^g = \tilde{a}_\tau^g + q(r = 1) \Delta a_\tau^g.$$

So the usual count update is now multiplied by the probability of selecting the update action.

This makes the interpretation very simple:

- if $q(r = 1) = 1$, we recover ordinary learning;
- if $q(r = 1) = 0$, no learning occurs;
- if $0 < q(r = 1) < 1$, the update is only partially admitted.

Another good way to say this is that Friston et al. [1] perform a Bayesian model average over two possibilities:

- the model in which the current datum is assimilated;
- the model in which it is not.

The resulting count update is the expectation under that binary mixture.

6.2.9 Learning Rate and Memory Scale η The learning scheme can also rescale the resulting concentration parameters using a memory scale η :

$$\tilde{a}_{\tau+1} = \frac{[\tilde{a}_\tau + q(r = 1) \Delta a] \eta}{\eta + q(r = 1)}.$$

Without this rescaling, repeated count updates would make the Dirichlet concentration parameters grow indefinitely. The parameter η sets an effective memory or concentration scale. Large η preserves more accumulated evidence, so each new admitted update has a smaller relative effect. Smaller η makes the learned mapping adapt more quickly. If the update is fully admitted, $q(r = 1) = 1$, then

$$\tilde{a}_{\tau+1} = \frac{(\tilde{a}_\tau + \Delta a) \eta}{\eta + 1}.$$

If the update is rejected, $q(r = 1) = 0$, then the rescaling leaves \tilde{a}_τ unchanged.

6.2.10 Precision of the Update Gate The parameter β controls how sharply expected free energy affects the update choice.

When β is small, the softmax is shallow, so the update probability changes only gradually with G . When β is large, the softmax becomes very sharp, and the Bayesian model average becomes close to an all-or-none choice:

- apply the update;
- do not apply the update.

So β plays the role of a precision parameter controlling how decisively the model accepts or rejects candidate learning updates.

6.3 Reference Implementation Extension: Transition Count Learning and Novelty

Friston et al. [1] develop the active-learning gate around likelihood counts \tilde{a} . The reference implementation [2] applies the same selective-learning logic to transition counts \tilde{b} and includes a transition-novelty contribution when it scores future paths. The candidate transition update mirrors the candidate likelihood update: from the inferred posteriors over states and paths at successive time steps,

$$\Delta b^f = \sum_{\tau} \hat{s}_{\tau}^f \otimes \hat{s}_{\tau-1}^f \otimes \hat{u}_{\tau-1}^f.$$

The increment fills in the cell of the transition tensor that was visited under the inferred state-path trajectory of factor f . As with Δa , nothing has yet been admitted: Δb^f is only the candidate update.

An analogous update gate $r \in \{0, 1\}$ is then applied, with the same Bayesian model average:

$$\tilde{b}_{\tau+1}^f = \tilde{b}_{\tau}^f + q(r = 1) \Delta b^f,$$

optionally damped by the same memory scale η . So the selective-learning logic is structurally identical to the one developed above for \tilde{a} ; the only thing that changes is which expected-information-gain term appears in the expected free energy that scores r .

For the likelihood, that term is likelihood novelty: roughly, how much the model expects to learn about A^g from the current observation, written W^g in Friston et al. [1]. For the transition tensor, there is an analogous transition novelty:

$$I^f = \text{expected information gain about } B^f$$

under the candidate \tilde{b}^f . The notation I^f matches reference implementation [2], where it is computed by the same wnorm-style construction used for W^g . A short caveat is worth flagging: this I^f is a novelty term about transition parameters, not Shannon mutual information; the symbol is reused because the reference implementation [2] uses it, but the conceptual content is the expected-information-gain term that drives Δb^f in the same way W^g drives Δa^g .

The practical consequence is that planning gains a second epistemic channel. Candidate paths can be epistemically valuable in two distinct ways: by clarifying the likelihood mapping (W^g) and by clarifying the transition dynamics (I^f). Both contributions show up in expected free energy, and both can drive exploratory behaviour.

6.4 Ungated Conjugate Updates for Outcome and Initial Priors

The remaining count tensors (outcome priors, initial-state priors, and initial-path priors) are updated more simply. There is no gating step: the candidate increment is admitted directly, then damped by the memory scale η . So these are pure conjugate Dirichlet updates with the standard damping.

Before writing the updates, one notational point has to be settled. The symbol c plays two distinct roles in Friston et al. [1]:

- **Fixed** C . When c encodes a goal, $P(o | c) = \text{Cat}(C)$ is a preferred-outcome distribution: the agent’s preferences over outcomes. This C is set externally, treated as part of the agent’s specification, and not updated from data. Outcome preferences are goals, not hypotheses.
- **Learnable** \tilde{c} . When c is treated as a Dirichlet random variable, it becomes a learnable count tensor whose mean encodes an empirical prior over outcomes at terminal time: the model’s running tally of what tends to occur, treated as a prior rather than as a goal. This is the object that gets updated from observations.

Conflating the two leads to the confusing-sounding claim "the agent learns its preferences from data." The Dirichlet update below applies only to \tilde{c} , not to fixed C . With that distinction in place, the conjugate updates are

$$\Delta c^g = O_T^g, \quad \Delta d^f = \hat{s}_0^f, \quad \Delta e^f = \hat{u}_0^f.$$

The empirical outcome prior accumulates the terminal observation; the initial-state prior accumulates the inferred initial-state belief; the initial-path prior accumulates the inferred initial-path belief. After damping,

$$\tilde{c}_{\tau+1}^g = \frac{(\tilde{c}_\tau^g + \Delta c^g) \eta}{\eta + 1},$$

and analogously for \tilde{d}^f and \tilde{e}^f . The same η that controls \tilde{a} and \tilde{b} controls these too.

Why no r gate here? The active-learning gate is motivated by the epistemic value of updating a predictive tensor: \tilde{a} shapes how outcomes are predicted from states, and \tilde{b} shapes how states evolve under paths, so updating them changes the information landscape of future inference. The objects \tilde{c} , \tilde{d} , \tilde{e} are simpler (an empirical outcome prior, an initial-state prior, and an initial-path prior) and they are not treated as epistemic predictive mappings in the same gated-update scheme. There is no comparable epistemic case for gating their update, so Friston et al. [1] treat them as ordinary conjugate updates with memory-scale damping and nothing more.

7 Structural Selection and Model Comparison

This section separates a structural principle from a concrete structure-building algorithm. Friston et al. [1] frame structural change through active selection and Bayesian model comparison; Section 8 describes the fast renormalisation group constructor that builds the hierarchy used in later examples.

7.1 Fixed-Point Account: Structural Change as Model Comparison

Inference updates hidden variables. Learning updates parameters. Active selection asks whether the model structure itself should be simplified or expanded. In Friston et al. [1], this is done with Bayesian model comparison.

Active selection concerns model structure, not just latent states or parameters. Inference optimizes posteriors over hidden variables, learning optimizes posteriors over parameters, and active selection compares alternative priors or alternative structures for those parameters.

7.2 Bayesian Model Reduction in a Shared Parameter Space

Friston et al. [1] first consider Bayesian model reduction. Start with a parent model whose Dirichlet prior over a likelihood tensor is a , and suppose that after assimilating data o the posterior counts are \tilde{a} . Now define a reduced model with prior counts a' . The question is how the model evidence changes if we replace the parent prior a by the reduced prior a' . Friston et al. [1] write

$$\Delta F = \log P(o | a) - \log P(o | a') = \log \mathcal{B}(\tilde{a}) + \log \mathcal{B}(a') - \log \mathcal{B}(a) - \log \mathcal{B}(\tilde{a} + a' - a),$$

with

$$\tilde{a}' = \tilde{a} + a' - a.$$

Here $\mathcal{B}(\cdot)$ is the multivariate beta function, i.e. the normalising constant of a Dirichlet distribution:

$$\mathcal{B}(a) = \frac{\prod_i \Gamma(a_i)}{\Gamma(\sum_i a_i)}.$$

For a likelihood tensor with independent Dirichlet columns, this notation means the product of this normalising constant over columns or parent configurations:

$$\mathcal{B}(a) := \prod_{\kappa} \mathcal{B}(a_{\kappa}).$$

To interpret

$$\tilde{a}' = \tilde{a} + a' - a,$$

define the effective count increment

$$N := \tilde{a} - a.$$

Then

$$\tilde{a} = a + N, \quad \tilde{a}' = a' + N,$$

so substituting $N = \tilde{a} - a$ gives

$$\tilde{a}' = \tilde{a} + a' - a.$$

Thus \tilde{a}' is the posterior the reduced model would have had if it had started from prior a' and then assimilated the same sufficient statistics.

If the data contribute counts N , then a Dirichlet-categorical model with prior a has

$$P(o | a) = \int P(o | \theta)P(\theta | a) d\theta = \frac{\mathcal{B}(a + N)}{\mathcal{B}(a)}.$$

Since the posterior counts under the parent model are $\tilde{a} = a + N$, the parent evidence is $\mathcal{B}(\tilde{a})/\mathcal{B}(a)$. Under the reduced prior a' , the same data would give posterior counts $a' + N = \tilde{a} + a' - a$, so the reduced evidence is

$$P(o | a') = \frac{\mathcal{B}(\tilde{a} + a' - a)}{\mathcal{B}(a')}.$$

Taking the log difference between these two evidence terms gives Equation 8 in Friston et al. [1]. The beta function is written as $\mathcal{B}(\cdot)$ here so it is not confused with the transition tensor B .

Here $P(o | a)$ is the marginal likelihood, or model evidence, under the model specified by prior a . So this is not the ordinary likelihood $P(o | A)$ for a particular parameter value A ; it is the probability of the data under the whole model defined by the prior counts a .

Variational free energy is

$$F(q) = D_{\text{KL}}(q(\theta) \| p(\theta | o)) - \log P(o).$$

At the optimum over q , this becomes

$$F^* \approx -\log P(o).$$

So in Equation 8 in Friston et al. [1], ΔF is really a difference in optimized free energies, or equivalently a difference in log model evidences. It is not the raw variational functional $F(q)$ before optimization.

This construction only works directly when the parent and reduced models live in the same ambient parameter space, so that a , a' , \tilde{a} , and \tilde{a}' all have the same shape. Equation 8 in Friston et al. [1] is therefore best read as a within-family reduction formula: the reduced model is represented by altered priors over the same coordinates, not by a literal change in tensor size.

If one truly adds or removes states, factors, or tensor dimensions, then a and a' generally no longer have the same shape. In that case,

$$\tilde{a}' = \tilde{a} + a' - a$$

cannot be interpreted as ordinary tensor addition unless both models are first embedded in a common larger parameter space. Friston et al. [1] do not spell out such an embedding, so Equation 8 should not, by itself, be read as a formula for arbitrary architectural changes.

7.3 Model Augmentation and Structural Priors

Friston et al. [1] then turn to the opposite operation: model augmentation. Here we compare a parent model m with an augmented model m' , and the posterior odds are written as

$$\log \frac{P(m | o)}{P(m' | o)} = \log \frac{P(o | m) P(m)}{P(o | m') P(m')} = \Delta F + \Delta G,$$

where

$$\Delta F = \log P(o | m) - \log P(o | m'),$$

and

$$\Delta G = \log P(m) - \log P(m').$$

This is just Bayesian model comparison in log form. ΔF says which model explains the current observation better, and ΔG says which model is preferred a priori. Friston et al. [1] interpret this prior term in active terms by linking it to expected free energy, so that structural changes can themselves be treated as actions that are favored when they are expected to improve future inference or control.

Equation 9 in Friston et al. [1] is more general than Equation 8. It does not require the parent and augmented models to share the same tensor shape, because it compares them only through their scalar evidences $P(o | m)$, $P(o | m')$, and priors $P(m)$, $P(m')$. For that reason, Equation 9 still applies when augmentation introduces genuinely new latent causes or new structural degrees of freedom.

In practice, reduction is easiest to interpret as comparing a parent model with simpler alternatives expressed in the same coordinate system, whereas augmentation is easiest to interpret as adding new latent causes, new columns of a likelihood mapping, or other new structural elements. Friston et al. [1] are much more explicit about augmentation in its structure-learning examples, where new latent causes are introduced to explain unique observations or unique blocks of observations.

8 Fast Structure Learning as the RG Operator

Section 7 explained the structural-selection principle of Friston et al. [1]: model structure is compared through evidence and expected-free-energy considerations. Section 4 supplies the temporal RGM form that this construction preserves: path-conditioned state transitions together with higher-level D and E priors over lower-level segments. Fast structure learning is the concrete constructive RG operator used to build an RGM hierarchy from data. The reference implementation [2] operationalizes the RG step by grouping sites, forming pattern-class states, counting transitions and paths, and passing summaries upward. It pursues compression and reusable structure directly; it is not a literal execution of the active-selection equations.

Fast structure learning is the part of the RGM construction that builds the hierarchy. It takes a sequence of probabilistic observations and repeatedly applies a renormalisation operator:

$$\mathcal{R}_n : Y^{(n)} \mapsto (M^{(n)}, Y^{(n+1)}).$$

$Y^{(n)}$ denotes the data available at level n , and $M^{(n)}$ denotes the generalized MDP learned at that level. The same model form is learned at every scale; the data being modelled changes from one level to the next.

At the first level, $Y^{(1)}$ contains the original observed sequence. At higher levels, $Y^{(n)}$ contains summaries produced by the level below. The hierarchy is therefore built by repeatedly turning lower-level posterior beliefs into higher-level observations.

It is useful to write the level- n data as a site-time-channel array:

$$Y_{i,t,c}^{(n)} \in \Delta^{K_{i,c}^{(n)} - 1}.$$

Each entry is a categorical probability vector. The indices have the following meanings:

- i indexes a site, such as a pixel, voxel, patch, or lower-level factor;
- t indexes time;
- c indexes the visible channel at that site.

The number of channels per site is denoted by m_n . At the first level, m_n depends on the data. For example, a grayscale site may have one channel, while an RGB site may have three. At higher RGM levels, the natural representation has two channels, $m_n = 2$, because each lower-level factor contributes a state-belief channel and a path-belief channel.

The fast learner does not search over arbitrary graphical models. Instead, it uses a direct sequence-based construction: it groups informative sites, compresses each group into hidden states, counts transitions and paths between those states, and passes the resulting state/path summaries upward.

8.1 Space and Time Scales

Two scales control the RG step:

$$dx_n = \text{maximum group size at level } n, \quad dt_n = \text{temporal stride at level } n.$$

The spatial scale dx_n bounds how many sites can be compressed into one hidden factor, where $|G_k^{(n)}| \leq dx_n$. This need not mean a literal square or cubic spatial block. In the information-based version of the reference implementation [2], it means that no learned group should contain more than dx_n sites.

The temporal scale dt_n controls temporal subsampling between levels. At level n , a learned group produces a sequence of state beliefs $\hat{s}_{k,t}^{(n)} = q(s_{k,t}^{(n)})$ and

path beliefs $\hat{u}_{k,t}^{(n)} = q(u_{k,t}^{(n)})$. The path $u_{k,t}^{(n)}$ labels the transition from the current state to the next state:

$$u_{k,t}^{(n)} : s_{k,t}^{(n)} \rightarrow s_{k,t+1}^{(n)}.$$

Therefore, if there are T_n state time points, $s_{k,1}^{(n)}, \dots, s_{k,T_n}^{(n)}$, there are only $T_n - 1$ transition time points:

$$s_{k,1}^{(n)} \rightarrow s_{k,2}^{(n)}, \quad s_{k,2}^{(n)} \rightarrow s_{k,3}^{(n)}, \quad \dots, \quad s_{k,T_n-1}^{(n)} \rightarrow s_{k,T_n}^{(n)}.$$

The next level receives only every dt_n -th transition time:

$$t_\tau = 1 + (\tau - 1)dt_n, \quad t_\tau \leq T_n - 1.$$

At those selected times, the lower-level state and path beliefs become the two channels of the next-level data: $Y_{k,\tau,1}^{(n+1)} = \hat{s}_{k,t_\tau}^{(n)}$ and $Y_{k,\tau,2}^{(n+1)} = \hat{u}_{k,t_\tau}^{(n)}$. This is temporal coarse-graining: higher levels model a slower, subsampled sequence of lower-level state and path beliefs.

8.2 Grouping Sites by Mutual Information

The first operation at level n is to partition the sites into groups:

$$\{1, \dots, N_n\} = G_1^{(n)} \cup \dots \cup G_{K_n}^{(n)}.$$

Each group $G_k^{(n)}$ will become one hidden-state factor.

8.2.1 Bundle Channels at Each Site Before comparing sites, the learner bundles the channels at each site into one site-level distribution. If site i has m_n channels, define

$$Z_{i,t}^{(n)} = Y_{i,t,1}^{(n)} \otimes Y_{i,t,2}^{(n)} \otimes \dots \otimes Y_{i,t,m_n}^{(n)}.$$

The Kronecker product forms a joint distribution over the channels at that site, under the factorized representation already being used. If $m_n = 1$, then $Z_{i,t}^{(n)} = Y_{i,t,1}^{(n)}$. If $m_n = 2$, as at any level after the first, the two channels have the form $Y_{i,\tau,1}^{(n)} = \hat{s}_{i,t_\tau}^{(n-1)}$ and $Y_{i,\tau,2}^{(n)} = \hat{u}_{i,t_\tau}^{(n-1)}$. The corresponding site-level distribution is

$$Z_{i,\tau}^{(n)} = \hat{s}_{i,t_\tau}^{(n-1)} \otimes \hat{u}_{i,t_\tau}^{(n-1)}.$$

Grouping is therefore performed over whole lower-level items, each represented by its paired state/path summary. The state channel and path channel are not grouped as separate objects. For each pair of sites (i, j) , the learner forms an empirical joint table by accumulating co-occurrences over time:

$$C_{ij}(a, b) = \sum_t Z_{i,t}^{(n)}(a) Z_{j,t}^{(n)}(b).$$

The indices a and b refer to bundled site-level values, not to the original channels separately. To make this concrete, suppose that at some higher level each site has a state channel and a path channel:

$$Y_{i,t,1}^{(n)} = q(s_i), \quad Y_{i,t,2}^{(n)} = q(u_i).$$

If the state channel has three possible values and the path channel has two possible values, then the bundled variable

$$Z_{i,t}^{(n)} = q(s_i) \otimes q(u_i)$$

has six possible joint values:

$$(1, 1), (1, 2), (2, 1), (2, 2), (3, 1), (3, 2).$$

The index a denotes one of these joint state-path values. If two sites each have six joint values, then C_{ij} is a 6×6 co-occurrence table.

For one-hot beliefs, a single time point adds one count to the cell corresponding to the realised pair of joint values. For soft beliefs, it adds fractional counts. If site i assigns probability 0.7 to joint value a , and site j assigns probability 0.4 to joint value b , then that time point contributes 0.7×0.4 to $C_{ij}(a, b)$.

Thus the mutual information is computed between whole bundled sites

$$I((s_i, u_i); (s_j, u_j)),$$

not separately between state-state, path-path, or state-path channels.

8.2.2 Score Site Pairs

After normalisation,

$$P_{ij}(a, b) = \frac{C_{ij}(a, b)}{\sum_{a,b} C_{ij}(a, b)},$$

the pair is scored by mutual information:

$$I_{ij} = \sum_{a,b} P_{ij}(a, b) \log \frac{P_{ij}(a, b)}{P_i(a)P_j(b)}.$$

Large I_{ij} means that the two sites carry shared temporal structure. If a site is constant over the sequence, it is not useful for discovering dynamical structure and does not form informative links to other sites.

8.2.3 Select Groups

The grouping problem can be stated as an optimisation problem. The aim is to choose a set of sites G whose members have large mutual information with one another. A natural within-group score is

$$\text{score}(G) = \sum_{i,j \in G} I_{ij}.$$

If we encode group membership with a binary vector

$$z_i = \begin{cases} 1, & i \in G, \\ 0, & i \notin G, \end{cases}$$

then this score can be written as $z^\top I z = \sum_{i,j} z_i I_{ij} z_j$. The product $z_i z_j$ is nonzero only when both sites are in the candidate group. Therefore, $z^\top I z$ sums the mutual information inside that group.

The direct formulation is $\max_z z^\top I z$ subject to

$$z_i \in \{0, 1\}, \quad \sum_i z_i \leq dx_n.$$

This objective defines a brute-force combinatorial problem: search over all possible groups, keep the group whose internal mutual information is largest, then repeat. Exhaustive search becomes expensive as the number of sites grows.

The spectral step is a relaxation of this problem. Instead of requiring z_i to be exactly 0 or 1, allow a continuous membership weight v_i . The relaxed problem is

$$\max_{\|v\|=1} v^\top I v.$$

The objective is

$$v^\top I v = \sum_{i,j} v_i I_{ij} v_j.$$

This quantity is large when large weights v_i and v_j are placed on pairs of sites with large mutual information I_{ij} . The relaxed problem therefore asks for a soft group: assign high continuous weight to sites that are strongly mutually informative.

By the Rayleigh quotient theorem, the maximiser of this relaxed problem is the principal eigenvector of the mutual-information matrix:

$$I v = \lambda_{\max} v.$$

Componentwise, this says

$$\lambda_{\max} v_i = \sum_j I_{ij} v_j,$$

or

$$v_i = \frac{1}{\lambda_{\max}} \sum_j I_{ij} v_j.$$

This equation gives a self-consistent interpretation of v_i as the membership score of site i . A site receives a large score when it has high mutual information with other sites that also receive large scores. This is the same self-reinforcing principle used in eigenvector centrality: a site is important for the candidate group when it is connected to other important sites.

The reference implementation [2] then turns this soft group into a hard group. For the current set of unassigned sites, it sorts the entries of the principal eigenvector by magnitude,

$$|v_{\pi_1}| \geq |v_{\pi_2}| \geq \dots,$$

keeps the largest entries up to the group-size bound dx_n , removes entries that are effectively zero, and declares the selected sites to be one group:

$$G = \{\pi_1, \dots, \pi_{\min(dx_n, |R|)}\}$$

after thresholding. The selected group is removed from the remaining sites R , and the procedure is repeated until every site has been assigned to a group.

The spectral step only decides which sites should be compressed together. It does not define the latent state space. The hidden states are defined in the next step, by the local pattern classes that occur inside the chosen group.

8.3 Local Patterns Become Hidden States

After grouping, each group is treated as a small local system. At every time point, the group has a joint visible configuration: the collection of all site-channel values inside that group. Call this configuration the local visible pattern of group k at time t and denote it by $z_{k,t}^{(n)}$. More explicitly, this pattern is the set of visible distributions for every site and channel in the group:

$$z_{k,t}^{(n)} = \left\{ Y_{i,t,c}^{(n)} : i \in G_k^{(n)}, c = 1, \dots, m_n \right\}.$$

8.3.1 One-Hot Patterns The key compression step is simple in the one-hot case: repeated local patterns are treated as the same hidden state. If the group contains two categorical sites and the realised pattern is

$$(A, Y),$$

then every later occurrence of (A, Y) receives the same hidden-state label. In that setting, "unique pattern" can be read literally.

For example, suppose a group contains two binary sites. At four time points, the local patterns might be

$$(0, 0), \quad (0, 1), \quad (0, 1), \quad (1, 1).$$

There are three unique patterns:

$$\xi_1 = (0, 0), \quad \xi_2 = (0, 1), \quad \xi_3 = (1, 1).$$

The hidden state of the group has three possible values:

$$s_k \in \{1, 2, 3\}.$$

The observed pattern sequence is then rewritten as the hidden-state label sequence

$$j_{k,1:4} = (1, 2, 2, 3).$$

In words, the hidden state is not an extra hidden feature. It is the label of the local pattern class currently expressed by the group.

8.3.2 Soft Patterns For soft probability vectors, the phrase "unique pattern" needs more care. Suppose the group contains two sites:

$$o_1 \in \Delta^2, \quad o_2 \in \Delta^2.$$

If the observations are one-hot, we may write

$$o_1 = (1, 0, 0), \quad o_2 = (0, 1, 0)$$

as the symbolic pattern (A, Y) . But if

$$o_1 = (0.70, 0.20, 0.10), \quad o_2 = (0.10, 0.80, 0.10),$$

there is no single realised pair (A, Y) . The local pattern is the pair of probability vectors themselves. Equivalently, it is a probabilistic configuration over the possible values of both sites.

The fast constructor handles this by grouping similar observed soft patterns into the same class. To compare two soft local patterns, first imagine flattening the whole group pattern at time t into one vector:

$$r_{k,t}^{(n)} = \text{vec} \left(\{Y_{i,t,c}^{(n)} : i \in G_k^{(n)}, c = 1, \dots, m_n\} \right).$$

This vector is not a symbolic tuple such as (A, Y) . It is just the concatenated probability vectors for all visible variables in the group.

For the sequence of local patterns

$$z_{k,1}^{(n)}, \dots, z_{k,T_n}^{(n)},$$

the reference implementation [2] computes a similarity matrix from normalised inner products:

$$S_{tt'} = \frac{\langle r_{k,t}^{(n)}, r_{k,t'}^{(n)} \rangle}{\|r_{k,t}^{(n)}\| \|r_{k,t'}^{(n)}\|}.$$

This is a cosine-like similarity between probability patterns after normalisation. It is high when the two soft group patterns are similar. The code then converts this similarity into a distance of the form

$$\delta_{tt'} = 2\sqrt{2} N_G (1 - S_{tt'}),$$

where N_G is the number of visible variables in the group. The exact scale is implementation-specific, but the role is simple: similar probability patterns have small distance, dissimilar probability patterns have large distance.

The code then thresholds this distance matrix:

$$M_{tt'} = \mathbf{1}\{\delta_{tt'} < 2\},$$

and applies a uniqueness operation to the rows of M . Two time points are assigned to the same hidden-state label when they have the same thresholded

distance profile to the other observed patterns. In other words, the constructor does not create a fixed grid over all possible soft vectors. It bins the soft patterns that actually occur in the structure-learning sequence.

This has two consequences. First, a hidden state is not always the name of a crisp symbolic tuple such as (A, Y) . In the soft case, it is the index of an observed probability-pattern class. Second, the learned state space is limited to the pattern classes seen during structure learning. The constructor assumes that the training sequence contains the reusable local configurations that will later be needed by the model. If a genuinely new configuration should become a new hidden state, the structure-learning step would have to be rerun or extended; ordinary inference with the learned model does not add new hidden states.

During later inference, a new observation is therefore not sent back through this uniqueness step to create a fresh class. It is evaluated under the already learned likelihoods A . If the new soft pattern resembles one learned class, inference assigns high posterior probability to the corresponding hidden state. If it lies between several learned classes, the posterior can become spread over those states. If it is far from every learned likelihood column, the model cannot represent it well: the result is poor evidence, large prediction error, or uncertain posterior beliefs, not automatic creation of a new state.

8.3.3 Pattern Classes Become States Across the structure-learning sequence, suppose group k is assigned L_k pattern classes, represented by

$$\{\xi_{k,1}^{(n)}, \dots, \xi_{k,L_k}^{(n)}\}.$$

Each distinct pattern class becomes one possible value of the hidden state $s_k^{(n)}$:

$$s_{k,t}^{(n)} = \ell \iff z_{k,t}^{(n)} \sim \xi_{k,\ell}^{(n)}.$$

Here \sim means that the local pattern belongs to the same discretised probability-pattern class as the representative $\xi_{k,\ell}^{(n)}$. In the deterministic examples below, \sim can be read as ordinary equality.

Thus the learner replaces the observed sequence of local patterns

$$z_{k,1}^{(n)}, z_{k,2}^{(n)}, \dots, z_{k,T_n}^{(n)}$$

by a sequence of hidden-state labels

$$j_{k,1}^{(n)}, j_{k,2}^{(n)}, \dots, j_{k,T_n}^{(n)}, \quad j_{k,t}^{(n)} \in \{1, \dots, L_k\}.$$

The same idea applies when the group has multiple channels per site. If each site has a state-belief channel and a path-belief channel, then a local pattern is the joint state/path-belief configuration across all sites in the group. Repeated configurations, or soft configurations that pass the same distance test, receive the same hidden-state label.

For example, suppose a higher-level group contains two lower-level sites:

$$G_k = \{1, 2\}.$$

Each site has two channels:

$$\text{channel 1} = \hat{s}_i = q(s_i), \quad \text{channel 2} = \hat{u}_i = q(u_i).$$

Suppose the beliefs are one-hot, with

$$\hat{s}_i \in \{A, B\}, \quad \hat{u}_i \in \{L, R\}.$$

At each time, site i is described by a pair

$$(\hat{s}_i, \hat{u}_i).$$

The group might have the following sequence over four time points:

$$\begin{aligned} t = 1 &: [(A, L), (A, L)], \\ t = 2 &: [(A, R), (B, R)], \\ t = 3 &: [(A, R), (B, R)], \\ t = 4 &: [(B, R), (B, L)]. \end{aligned}$$

Each bracket is the full local pattern of the group, including both channels for both sites. There are three pattern classes:

$$\begin{aligned} \xi_1 &= [(A, L), (A, L)], \\ \xi_2 &= [(A, R), (B, R)], \\ \xi_3 &= [(B, R), (B, L)]. \end{aligned}$$

The group hidden state has three possible values,

$$s_k \in \{1, 2, 3\},$$

and the pattern sequence becomes

$$j_{k,1:4} = (1, 2, 2, 3).$$

In this example, $s_k = 2$ does not mean only that site 1 has state A , or only that a path is R . It denotes the whole repeated configuration

$$[(\hat{s}_1 = A, \hat{u}_1 = R), (\hat{s}_2 = B, \hat{u}_2 = R)].$$

8.3.4 Likelihoods Average the Assigned Patterns Once the hidden-state labels have been assigned, the learner asks: when the group is in hidden state ℓ , what does each site/channel in the group usually look like? This question defines the likelihood mapping.

For a group $G_k^{(n)}$, the hidden state $s_k^{(n)}$ explains all visible variables inside the group. For every site $i \in G_k^{(n)}$ and every channel $c = 1, \dots, m_n$, the learner estimates a likelihood distribution $P(y_{i,c}^{(n)} | s_k^{(n)})$. This distribution says: if the group is in hidden state ℓ , how likely is site i , channel c , to take value y ?

The representative $\xi_{k,\ell}^{(n)}$ should not be confused with the learned likelihood column. The representative names the pattern class and fixes the state label. The likelihood column is built from all training time points assigned to that class. So if two nearby soft vectors are assigned to the same class, the model does not choose one of them as the value of the state. It adds both into the Dirichlet counts.

The estimate is obtained by counting across all time points assigned to state ℓ . If $j_{k,t}^{(n)} = \ell$, then time t is an example of hidden state ℓ . At that time, the observed distribution for site i , channel c , is $Y_{i,t,c}^{(n)}$. Therefore, the count for visible value y under hidden state ℓ is

$$\tilde{a}_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(y, \ell) = a_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(y, \ell) + \sum_{t: j_{k,t}^{(n)} = \ell} Y_{i,t,c}^{(n)}(y).$$

This equation says to add up all evidence for value y from all time points where the group was in hidden state ℓ . If the observations are one-hot, this is an ordinary count. If the observations are soft probability vectors, this is a fractional count.

This is why the soft case remains meaningful after discretisation. The state label is hard, because each training time point is assigned to one pattern class. But the likelihood counts remain soft, because the full probability vectors are accumulated inside that class. For example, if two time points are assigned to the same class ℓ and the observed vectors for a binary channel are

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0.70 \\ 0.30 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \begin{bmatrix} 0.60 \\ 0.40 \end{bmatrix},$$

then their contribution to the likelihood column is

$$a_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(:, \ell) \leftarrow a_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(:, \ell) + \begin{bmatrix} 1.30 \\ 0.70 \end{bmatrix}.$$

After normalisation, this column has mean

$$\frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1.30 \\ 0.70 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.65 \\ 0.35 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The resulting hidden state does not say "the site was definitely value 1." It says "this pattern class tends to generate this distribution over visible values."

For example, suppose site i , channel c , is binary $y \in \{0, 1\}$. Suppose hidden state $\ell = 2$ occurs at three time points, $t = 2, 3, 6$. At those times, suppose the visible values are

$$Y_{i,2,c}^{(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Y_{i,3,c}^{(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Y_{i,6,c}^{(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Then the count vector for hidden state $\ell = 2$ is

$$a_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(:, 2) = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} + \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 2 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Under hidden state 2, this site/channel was therefore observed once in value 0 and twice in value 1.

These counts parameterise a Dirichlet distribution over the corresponding likelihood column:

$$A_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(:, \ell) \sim \text{Dir}(\tilde{a}_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(:, \ell)).$$

The mean likelihood is

$$\mathbb{E}[A_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(y, \ell)] = \frac{\tilde{a}_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(y, \ell)}{\sum_{y'} \tilde{a}_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(y', \ell)}.$$

In the example above,

$$\mathbb{E}[A_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(:, 2)] = \begin{bmatrix} 1/3 \\ 2/3 \end{bmatrix}.$$

Thus, if the group is in hidden state 2, this visible channel is expected to show value 1 with probability 2/3.

The generative interpretation is

$$P(y_{i,t,c}^{(n)} = y \mid s_{k,t}^{(n)} = \ell, A_{k,i,c}^{(n)}) = A_{k,i,c}^{(n)}(y, \ell).$$

That is, the hidden state of the group generates each visible site/channel through its own likelihood mapping:

$$s_k^{(n)} \longrightarrow Y_{i,c}^{(n)} \quad \text{for every } i \in G_k^{(n)}, c = 1, \dots, m_n.$$

A group state is therefore a compact cause of the whole local visible pattern. The likelihood tells us what each part of that pattern should look like when the group is in a given state.

8.4 Transitions and Paths

8.4.1 Count Transitions Once the hidden-state sequence has been induced, the learner counts transitions $j_{k,t}^{(n)} \rightarrow j_{k,t+1}^{(n)}$. The transition count asks: when the group is currently in state s , which state does it move to next? In an ordinary Markov model, this would be enough. In an RGM, the transition also depends

on a path variable u . The path variable indexes which transition rule is being used.

These counts define Dirichlet parameters $\tilde{b}_k^{(n)}(s', s, u)$ for the transition tensor, with the generative interpretation

$$B_k^{(n)}(:, s, u) \sim \text{Dir}(\tilde{b}_k^{(n)}(:, s, u)),$$

and

$$P(s_{k,t+1}^{(n)} = s' \mid s_{k,t}^{(n)} = s, u_{k,t}^{(n)} = u, B_k^{(n)}) = B_k^{(n)}(s', s, u).$$

The entry $b_k^{(n)}(s', s, u)$ is the Dirichlet count for transitions in which s denotes the current state, u denotes the path, and s' denotes the next state. Equivalently, each value of u selects a transition matrix $B_k^{(n)}(:, :, u)$.

8.4.2 Add Paths When Branching Is Needed The path variable u indexes a transition regime. In the fast construction, a path is created only when it is needed to explain branching dynamics. If a state s always has the same successor, one path slice is enough. If the same state sometimes goes to different successors, additional path slices are introduced.

For example, suppose the hidden-state label sequence for a group is $j_{k,1:4}^{(n)} = (1, 2, 1, 3)$. Suppose the observed transitions are $1 \rightarrow 2$, $2 \rightarrow 1$, and $1 \rightarrow 3$. The first two transitions can be placed in the same path slice, because they do not conflict: path $u = 1$ can say that state 1 goes to state 2, and state 2 goes to state 1:

$$B(:, :, 1) : \quad 1 \rightarrow 2, \quad 2 \rightarrow 1.$$

The third transition, $1 \rightarrow 3$, conflicts with the existing rule for state 1 under path $u = 1$, because path $u = 1$ already maps $1 \rightarrow 2$. A new path slice is therefore introduced:

$$B(:, :, 2) : \quad 1 \rightarrow 3.$$

In this example, the same current state 1 can have two different successors. The path variable disambiguates which successor is expected:

$$u = 1 : 1 \rightarrow 2, \quad u = 2 : 1 \rightarrow 3.$$

Thus a path is not initially a semantic label such as "move left" or "enter object". It is an empirical transition rule: u is the transition slice that explains $s_t \rightarrow s_{t+1}$. This transition learning makes the hierarchy temporal rather than merely spatial. Each level learns not only what local patterns exist, but also how those patterns move through a state space.

8.5 Passing Summaries Upward

For each learned group, the fast learner constructs posterior beliefs over states and paths:

$$\hat{s}_{k,t}^{(n)} = q(s_{k,t}^{(n)}), \quad \hat{u}_{k,t}^{(n)} = q(u_{k,t}^{(n)}).$$

In the fast construction, these are usually one-hot beliefs derived from the unique-state and transition-path labels.

This one-hot property is specific to the fast structure-learning construction. The pattern-class step assigns each time point to a definite hidden-state label, so the state belief is a degenerate categorical distribution $\hat{s}_{k,t}^{(n)} = e_\ell$. Similarly, each observed transition is assigned to a definite path slice, so the path belief is also degenerate $\hat{u}_{k,t}^{(n)} = e_h$.

The notation $q(s)$ and $q(u)$ is still useful because these objects are probability vectors, and because the more general RGM formalism can accommodate soft posterior beliefs. However, in this fast constructor, the observations passed upward are hard state/path summaries.

The next-level data are made from these beliefs. For selected lower-level transition times t_τ , we have $Y_{k,\tau,1}^{(n+1)} = \hat{s}_{k,t_\tau}^{(n)}$, and $Y_{k,\tau,2}^{(n+1)} = \hat{u}_{k,t_\tau}^{(n)}$. Each retained group at level n becomes one site at level $n+1$, with two channels:

$$Y_k^{(n+1)} = (\text{state belief of group } k, \text{path belief of group } k).$$

For example, suppose a level- n group has three possible states and two possible paths. At a selected time t_τ , its posterior beliefs might be

$$\hat{s}_{k,t_\tau}^{(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \hat{u}_{k,t_\tau}^{(n)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The corresponding site at level $n+1$ has two visible channels at time τ :

$$Y_{k,\tau,1}^{(n+1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}, \quad Y_{k,\tau,2}^{(n+1)} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix}.$$

The first channel says which lower-level state was inferred. The second channel says which lower-level path was inferred.

The fast implementation may discard groups whose dynamics are constant or too uninformative to support another level of structure learning. This filtering changes which groups are retained, but it does not change the conceptual RG step: retained state/path summaries become the data for the next level.

Thus the recursion is: lower-level inference becomes higher-level data. The next level does not model the raw observations directly. It models the posterior state/path summaries produced by the level below.

8.6 How Hierarchical D and E Links Arise

8.6.1 Reading Higher-Level Likelihoods Downward as D and E The vertical mappings D and E are easiest to understand as ordinary likelihood mappings seen from a different level of the hierarchy.

The earlier discussion of local pattern classes described how a hidden state is connected to a visible channel by an A -matrix. The index notation changes

slightly here to avoid overloading k . In the level- n likelihood $A_{k,i,c}^{(n)}$, k indexed the group whose hidden state generated visible site i . At level $n + 1$, each retained level- n group becomes a visible site, so we reserve k for that lower-level child site and use κ for the higher-level group whose hidden state predicts it:

$$P(Y_{k,c}^{(n+1)} = y \mid s_{\kappa}^{(n+1)} = \ell, A_{\kappa,k,c}^{(n+1)}) = A_{\kappa,k,c}^{(n+1)}(y, \ell).$$

Here $s_{\kappa}^{(n+1)}$ is a hidden state at level $n + 1$, and $Y_{k,c}^{(n+1)}$ is one visible channel of site k at that same level. The matrix is learned by the same counting rule as before: when the higher-level state is ℓ , count which values appear in the visible channel.

At the first level, the visible channels are literal observations, such as pixels, colours, features, or discretised sensor values. In that case the learned mapping is simply called A , because it maps hidden states to observations. At any level above the first, the visible channels are no longer raw observations. They are the lower level's state and path summaries, where $Y_{k,\tau,1}^{(n+1)} = \hat{s}_{k,t_{\tau}}^{(n)}$ and $Y_{k,\tau,2}^{(n+1)} = \hat{u}_{k,t_{\tau}}^{(n)}$.

8.6.2 The Initial State and Path Are Initial Relative to a Segment

The mappings D and E specify how a higher-level state generates the beginning of a lower-level segment. Here, "initial" does not mean the first time point of the entire lower-level sequence. It means the first time point of the lower-level segment currently being generated by a higher-level state.

To see this, recall that the higher level runs on a slower time scale. A higher-level time point τ corresponds to a selected lower-level transition time t_{τ} . This selected time marks the beginning of a lower-level segment. Within that segment, we reset the local time coordinate so that the segment begins at local time 0:

$$s_{k,0}^{(n,\tau)} \equiv s_{k,t_{\tau}}^{(n)}, \quad u_{k,0}^{(n,\tau)} \equiv u_{k,t_{\tau}}^{(n)}.$$

The superscript (n, τ) means: level n , in the lower-level segment associated with higher-level time τ . Thus, $s_{k,0}^{(n,\tau)}$ is not necessarily the state of group k at the beginning of the whole sequence. It is the state of group k at the beginning of the segment selected by τ . Likewise, $u_{k,0}^{(n,\tau)}$ is the path at the beginning of that segment.

For readability, the segment index τ is suppressed below. Thus $s_{k,0}^{(n)}$ and $u_{k,0}^{(n)}$ should be read as the initial state and initial path of the lower-level segment currently being predicted.

The fast learner still uses the same likelihood-counting rule as before. What changes is the interpretation of the visible channels at level $n + 1$. At the first level, visible channels correspond to raw observations. At higher levels, the visible channels are summaries produced by the level below. In particular, the first channel contains lower-level state beliefs, and the second channel contains lower-level path beliefs, where $Y_{k,\tau,1}^{(n+1)} = \hat{s}_{k,t_{\tau}}^{(n)}$ and $Y_{k,\tau,2}^{(n+1)} = \hat{u}_{k,t_{\tau}}^{(n)}$.

The first channel therefore tells the higher-level model which lower-level state was present at the beginning of the corresponding segment. The likelihood table

learned for this channel can be read downward as a prior over lower-level initial states. This is the D mapping: $\tilde{d}_{k,\kappa}^{(n)}(s, \ell) \equiv \tilde{a}_{\kappa,k,1}^{(n+1)}(s, \ell)$. Equivalently,

$$P(s_{k,0}^{(n)} = s \mid s_{\kappa}^{(n+1)} = \ell, D_{k,\kappa}^{(n)}) = D_{k,\kappa}^{(n)}(s, \ell).$$

This says that if the higher-level hidden state $s_{\kappa}^{(n+1)}$ is in state ℓ , then D gives a distribution over the state with which lower-level group k should begin its segment.

The second channel tells the higher-level model which lower-level path was present at the beginning of the corresponding segment. The likelihood table learned for this channel can be read downward as a prior over lower-level initial paths. This is the E mapping: $\tilde{e}_{k,\kappa}^{(n)}(u, \ell) \equiv \tilde{a}_{\kappa,k,2}^{(n+1)}(u, \ell)$. Equivalently,

$$P(u_{k,0}^{(n)} = u \mid s_{\kappa}^{(n+1)} = \ell, E_{k,\kappa}^{(n)}) = E_{k,\kappa}^{(n)}(u, \ell).$$

This says that if the higher-level hidden state $s_{\kappa}^{(n+1)}$ is in state ℓ , then E gives a distribution over the path with which lower-level group k should begin its segment.

Thus D and E are not new kinds of conditional probability tables. They are ordinary likelihood tables learned at level $n + 1$, but their visible variables are lower-level latent summaries rather than raw observations. Their names change because their role changes when the hierarchy is read downward. In short, D and E initialise every lower-level segment generated by a higher-level state, not just the first segment in the whole sequence.

For example, suppose a higher-level state ℓ is learned from time points at which lower-level factor k is usually in state 3 and usually using path 1. The state-channel likelihood has most of its mass on lower state 3, and when read downward this becomes a D prior that initialises factor k in state 3. The path-channel likelihood has most of its mass on lower path 1, and when read downward this becomes an E prior that initialises the lower-level transition regime.

The upward and downward readings are therefore two views of the same learned relation. During structure learning, lower-level posterior states and paths are sent upward as data. During generation or hierarchical inference, the higher-level state predicts those same quantities downward as empirical priors:

$$\text{higher state} \longrightarrow \begin{cases} \text{lower initial state} & \text{via } D, \\ \text{lower initial path} & \text{via } E. \end{cases}$$

This gives the recursive RGM pattern:

states generate paths, paths generate states, and higher states initialise lower states and paths.

8.7 Summary of the RG Operator

The fast structure-learning operator proceeds in four stages. First, sites are grouped according to their mutual information. Second, repeated local patterns

within each group are compressed into hidden-state classes. Third, transitions between those classes are counted to construct likelihood and transition models together with state and path summaries. Finally, the resulting state and path beliefs are passed upward to become the observations of the next level.

The key ideas are:

- the data at each level are sites over time, with one or more visible channels per site;
- channels at a site are bundled before mutual information is computed between sites;
- grouping decides which sites should share a hidden factor;
- the hidden states of a group are the local pattern classes observed in that group;
- paths are learned transition slices between those hidden states;
- each retained group sends two channels upward: its state belief and its path belief;
- those two upward channels become the source of the downward D and E priors in the recursive generative model.

In short, fast structure learning preserves the generalized MDP form while replacing each level’s observations by coarser state/path summaries from the level below.

8.8 Supplementary Note: Adapting a Learned Hierarchy to a New Bottom Interface

The RG operator itself is complete once the learned hierarchy passes state/path summaries upward and reads higher-level predictions downward through D and E . The following adaptation step is useful when a learned hierarchy must later be reused with a different bottom task interface, but it is not required for the core renormalisation construction.

The RG operator learns a hierarchy from the data it is given. At the bottom of the learned hierarchy, the data are the first-level visible variables

$$Y_{i,t,c}^{(1)}$$

The learned first level $M^{(1)}$ explains these variables using the machinery introduced above: groups $G_k^{(1)}$, hidden states $s_k^{(1)}$, paths $u_k^{(1)}$, likelihoods $A_{k,i,c}^{(1)}$, and transitions $B_k^{(1)}$.

In a complete model, however, the variables used during structure learning need not be the variables directly available during later inference. The structure-learning data might be a clean state sequence, a segmented feature sequence, or any other representation that is useful for learning the hierarchy. The final model may instead receive a different set of low-level observations, and it may include extra controllable or contextual variables. In that case, the learned first level is not discarded; it is used as an interface bridge.

For example, suppose structure learning was given a clean sequence for one visible feature:

$$Y_{i,t,1}^{(1)} \in \{\text{closed}, \text{open}\}.$$

The first-level hidden state $s_k^{(1)}$ is then just the pattern class of that feature. In the simplest case, $dx_1 = 1$, each group contains one input site:

$$G_k^{(1)} = \{i\}.$$

The learned state space therefore mirrors the values that this single feature can take. The two learned states decode as

$$s_k^{(1)} = 1 \mapsto \text{closed}, \quad s_k^{(1)} = 2 \mapsto \text{open}.$$

In this special case, the first-level hidden state is almost a relabelling of the input feature. The useful learned object is not a new spatial abstraction, but the transition structure over that feature. The learned paths can encode transitions such as

$$\text{closed} \rightarrow \text{open} \rightarrow \text{closed}.$$

However, later, the final model may not observe "closed" or "open" directly. It may receive a noisy measurement \bar{o}_t , such as a brightness or pressure reading, whose likelihood depends on the same underlying variable:

$$P(\bar{o}_t | \bar{Y}_{i,t,1}^{(1)}).$$

The bottom level must therefore be modified to include this new observation model. The learned hierarchy still supplies expectations about when $\bar{Y}_{i,t,1}^{(1)}$ should be closed or open. The interface bridge connects the learned state $s_k^{(1)}$ to the replacement variable $\bar{Y}_{i,t,1}^{(1)}$.

The general operation is

$$(M^{(1)}, M^{(2)}, \dots, M^{(L)}) \mapsto (\bar{M}^{(1)}, M^{(2)}, \dots, M^{(L)}).$$

Here $\bar{M}^{(1)}$ is a replacement bottom level. The bar does not mean a new scale; it means that the first level has been rewritten so that it can accept the variables and observations required by the final model. The higher levels $M^{(2)}, \dots, M^{(L)}$ are kept, because they encode the learned coarse-scale temporal structure.

The learned likelihood from earlier is the bridge between these two bottom-level descriptions:

$$A_{k,i,c}^{(1)}(y, \alpha) = P(Y_{i,c}^{(1)} = y | s_k^{(1)} = \alpha, A_{k,i,c}^{(1)}), \quad i \in G_k^{(1)}.$$

It says what value the first-level visible variable $Y_{i,c}^{(1)}$ tends to have when the learned pattern-class state is α . If the replacement model uses the same value space as a hidden or interface variable, we write that replacement variable as $\bar{Y}_{i,c}^{(1)}$. The learned likelihood can then be read as

$$s_k^{(1)} \xrightarrow{A_{k,i,c}^{(1)}} \bar{Y}_{i,c}^{(1)}.$$

8.8.1 Project First-Level Transitions Into Replacement Variables The learned first-level transition for group k has already been introduced as

$$B_k^{(1)}(\alpha', \alpha, u) = P(s_{k,t+1}^{(1)} = \alpha' \mid s_{k,t}^{(1)} = \alpha, u_{k,t}^{(1)} = u, B_k^{(1)}).$$

This transition is expressed over learned pattern-class states α . If the replacement bottom level uses $\bar{Y}_{i,c}^{(1)}$ as one of its state variables, then the transition must be expressed in the value space of that replacement variable.

The target is a transition over the replacement variable:

$$P(\bar{Y}_{i,t+1,c}^{(1)} = y' \mid \bar{Y}_{i,t,c}^{(1)} = y, u_{k,t}^{(1)} = u).$$

The learned model does not contain this transition directly. It contains the transition over learned states,

$$P(s_{k,t+1}^{(1)} = \alpha' \mid s_{k,t}^{(1)} = \alpha, u_{k,t}^{(1)} = u, B_k^{(1)}) = B_k^{(1)}(\alpha', \alpha, u),$$

and the likelihood that decodes learned states into visible values,

$$P(\bar{Y}_{i,c}^{(1)} = y \mid s_k^{(1)} = \alpha, A_{k,i,c}^{(1)}) = A_{k,i,c}^{(1)}(y, \alpha).$$

First ask what the next replacement value should be if the current learned state is α and the path is u . Marginalising over the next learned state gives

$$\begin{aligned} P(y' \mid \alpha, u) &= \sum_{\alpha'} P(y' \mid \alpha', \alpha, u) P(\alpha' \mid \alpha, u) \\ &= \sum_{\alpha'} P(y' \mid \alpha') P(\alpha' \mid \alpha, u) \\ &= \sum_{\alpha'} \mu(\tilde{a}_{k,i,c}^{(1)})(y', \alpha') \mu(\tilde{b}_k^{(1)})(\alpha', \alpha, u). \end{aligned}$$

The second line uses the generative assumption that once the next learned state α' is known, the next value y' no longer depends on the previous learned state α or the path u .

The replacement bottom level starts from a current value y , not a current learned state α . To use the learned transition, we need a way to embed y into the learned state space. Write this reverse map as

$$R_{k,i,c}^{(1)}(\alpha, y) \approx P(s_k^{(1)} = \alpha \mid \bar{Y}_{i,c}^{(1)} = y).$$

Then

$$\begin{aligned} P(y' \mid y, u) &= \sum_{\alpha} P(y' \mid \alpha, y, u) P(\alpha \mid y, u) \\ &\approx \sum_{\alpha} P(y' \mid \alpha, u) R_{k,i,c}^{(1)}(\alpha, y) \\ &= \sum_{\alpha', \alpha} \mu(\tilde{a}_{k,i,c}^{(1)})(y', \alpha') \mu(\tilde{b}_k^{(1)})(\alpha', \alpha, u) R_{k,i,c}^{(1)}(\alpha, y). \end{aligned}$$

Thus, for each path u , the induced transition over the replacement variable is

$$\bar{B}_{i,c}^{(1)}(y', y, u) = \text{norm}_{y'} \sum_{\alpha', \alpha} \mu(\tilde{a}_{k,i,c}^{(1)})(y', \alpha') \mu(\tilde{b}_k^{(1)})(\alpha', \alpha, u) R_{k,i,c}^{(1)}(\alpha, y).$$

The three factors have distinct roles: $R_{k,i,c}^{(1)}$ embeds the current replacement value y into beliefs over learned states, $B_k^{(1)}$ advances the learned state under path u , and $A_{k,i,c}^{(1)}$ decodes the next learned state back into the replacement value y' . The normalisation over y' ensures that each column is a categorical distribution over next values.

The reverse map is the only delicate part. The likelihood $A_{k,i,c}^{(1)}$ gives $P(y | \alpha)$, not $P(\alpha | y)$. When the learned likelihood is close to deterministic, a simple practical choice is

$$R_{k,i,c}^{(1)} \approx (A_{k,i,c}^{(1)})^\top.$$

This gives the compact matrix expression

$$\bar{B}_{i,c}^{(1)}(:, :, u) = \text{norm} \left(A_{k,i,c}^{(1)} B_k^{(1)}(:, :, u) (A_{k,i,c}^{(1)})^\top \right).$$

The transpose is not a new generative assumption. It is a practical reverse projection from the replacement variable into the learned state space. If $A_{k,i,c}^{(1)}$ is broad or strongly many-to-one, then an explicitly constructed inverse mapping $R_{k,i,c}^{(1)}$ is conceptually cleaner.

For a small example, suppose a learned first-level state has two pattern classes:

$$\alpha = 1 \mapsto \text{off}, \quad \alpha = 2 \mapsto \text{on}.$$

If path u learned the transition

$$\alpha = 1 \rightarrow \alpha = 2,$$

then the projected transition over the replacement variable contains

$$\text{off} \rightarrow \text{on}.$$

The final bottom level can then use the learned temporal expectation while receiving observations through whatever likelihood is appropriate for the final task.

8.8.2 Translate the Downward D Priors The discussion above explained that a higher-level likelihood over the lower state channel can be read downward as a D prior. Before the replacement, a higher-level state $s_\kappa^{(2)} = \ell$ predicts the initial learned first-level state:

$$D_{k,\kappa}^{(1)}(\alpha, \ell) = P(s_{k,0}^{(1)} = \alpha | s_\kappa^{(2)} = \ell).$$

After the bottom level is replaced, the corresponding lower variable may be $\bar{Y}_{i,0,c}^{(1)}$, not the learned pattern-class state $s_{k,0}^{(1)}$. The adapted D prior is therefore obtained by composing the old D prior with the first-level likelihood:

$$\bar{D}_{i,c,\kappa}^{(1)}(y, \ell) = \sum_{\alpha} \mu(\tilde{a}_{k,i,c}^{(1)}(y, \alpha)) \mu(\tilde{d}_{k,\kappa}^{(1)}(\alpha, \ell))$$

Equivalently,

$$\bar{D}_{i,c,\kappa}^{(1)} = \text{norm} \left(A_{k,i,c}^{(1)} D_{k,\kappa}^{(1)} \right).$$

This says that a higher-level state that used to initialise a learned first-level state now initialises the replacement-level variable predicted by that learned state.

For example, suppose a higher-level state ℓ predicts that group k should begin in a learned state whose likelihood column mostly emits "on." Then the adapted prior satisfies

$$\bar{D}_{i,c,\kappa}^{(1)}(\text{on}, \ell) \text{ is large.}$$

The higher level has not changed its event model. Only the bottom-level language has changed: the prediction is now expressed in the variable used by the replacement interface.

8.8.3 Reuse the E Priors When Paths Are Preserved The E mapping discussed above predicts the lower-level initial path:

$$E_{k,\kappa}^{(1)}(u, \ell) = P(u_{k,0}^{(1)} = u \mid s_{\kappa}^{(2)} = \ell).$$

The adaptation above keeps the same path labels u . What changes is the transition matrix selected by a path. Before adaptation, path u selected

$$B_k^{(1)}(:, :, u) \text{ over learned states } s_k^{(1)}.$$

After adaptation, the same path selects

$$\bar{B}_{i,c}^{(1)}(:, :, u) \text{ over replacement values } \bar{Y}_{i,c}^{(1)}.$$

Therefore the path prior can be reused:

$$\bar{E}_{i,c,\kappa}^{(1)}(u, \ell) = E_{k,\kappa}^{(1)}(u, \ell).$$

In words, the higher level still predicts which lower-level transition regime should be active. The transition regime now acts on the replacement-level variable rather than on the learned pattern-class state used during structure learning. If the replacement bottom level merges, splits, or renames paths, then this copying step should be replaced by an explicit path remapping. If the path labels are preserved, E can be reused directly.

8.8.4 Reattach the Hierarchy to the New Bottom Level The final step is to attach the higher-level predictions to the corresponding factors in $\bar{M}^{(1)}$. Thus the vertical relation

$$s_{\kappa}^{(2)} \longrightarrow \begin{cases} s_{k,0}^{(1)} & \text{via } D_{k,\kappa}^{(1)}, \\ u_{k,0}^{(1)} & \text{via } E_{k,\kappa}^{(1)} \end{cases}$$

is replaced by

$$s_{\kappa}^{(2)} \longrightarrow \begin{cases} \bar{Y}_{i,0,c}^{(1)} & \text{via } \bar{D}_{i,c,\kappa}^{(1)}, \\ \bar{u}_{i,c,0}^{(1)} & \text{via } \bar{E}_{i,c,\kappa}^{(1)}. \end{cases}$$

The replacement bottom level may also contain variables that were not part of the structure-learning data at all. These variables are not automatically given RGM parents. Their priors, transitions, and likelihoods must be supplied by the task model unless an explicit bridge to the learned hierarchy is constructed.

No new structure learning occurs in this adaptation step. The learned hierarchy is not relearned from the new observations. Rather, the first-level likelihood learned by the RG operator is used as a change of variables:

learned pattern-class state \longleftrightarrow variable used by the replacement bottom level.

This preserves the learned higher-level event structure while replacing the bottom interface. The final model can therefore use the learned state and path expectations while still receiving whatever observations and inputs are appropriate for the final task.

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